

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D4.1 – New protocols for studying the biological and paleobiological materials and for assessing diagenetic processes

v1.0

Deliverables information

Work package	WP4
Deliverable leader	UNIBO
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Deliverable status	Final
Deliverable version	V1.0
Date	22 December 2025

Deliverable history

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Institution(s)
V0.1	November 22 nd , 2025	adding text sections and contributions	All partners
V1.0	December 22 st , 2025	final version of common text, contributions homogenization and refinement	UNIBO

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Executive Summary

This report is part of the work performed in the project PNRR PE 5 "CHANGES", and specifically in Spoke 5 "Science and Technologies for Sustainable Diagnostics for Cultural Heritage", WP4 "Advanced diagnostics and scientific methods for organic material"

It presents and discusses the results obtained in the project, planned as: **R4.1 Development and implementation of digital, AI-based methods, chemical/physical and molecular approaches for studying the biological and palaeobiological materials** and constitutes one of the Deliverables produced: *D4.1 – New protocols for studying the biological and paleobiological materials and for assessing diagenetic processes.*

The scope of this report is to present and discuss the activities performed in WP4 by the research partners involved.

The **UNIBO Cultural Heritage Department** integrated analytical study of dental mineralized tissues offers a powerful framework for reconstructing life histories in an archaeological population, yielding information that is rarely accessible from other skeletal elements. Histological investigation of dental enamel, combining classical histomorphometry with histochemical analysis via LA-ICP-MS, offers the opportunity to examine the behaviour of enamel-forming cells during early-life stress episodes. This dual approach provides a more refined interpretation of the potential causes and developmental timing of enamel disturbances. Furthermore, coupling histomorphometric data with computer-based analytical algorithms present a promising method for estimating age-at-death in adults through dental cementum analysis. Since accurate age estimation in adults remains one of the most challenging aspects of biological profile reconstructions, this innovative approach has the potential to substantially improve both precision and reliability for this purpose.

The overarching goal of the **UNIBO Chemistry Department** is to develop rapid, reliable, and minimally destructive analytical approaches for archaeological biomaterials. This includes: improving the characterization of burned bones through portable IR and NIR spectroscopy coupled with chemometric analysis; assessing cellulose preservation in archaeological wood using SWIR hyperspectral imaging to optimize sampling for radiocarbon dating; evaluating long-term amino acid preservation in fossil enamel as a proxy for intra-crystalline organic retention; and advancing fast, low-cost detection of amelogenins through innovative biosensor platforms. Together, these activities aim to enhance diagnostic capabilities, refine sampling strategies, and broaden the analytical toolkit available for archaeological research.

The **UNIFI (BIO)** project aims to shed new light on the lives of the people of Pompeii and on other very important samples (i.e Grotta delle Mura individual) by combining the most advanced methods in genomics, bioarchaeology and biochemical analysis. Thanks to modern palaeogenomic techniques, researchers can now extract and study DNA preserved in ancient human remains, even when the material is highly degraded. By applying these

methods to the skeletal remains and dental calculus of more than 170 Pompeii inhabitants, the study seeks to reconstruct not only their biological characteristics—such as sex, physical appearance, genetic traits, intolerances and diseases—but also their family relationships and patterns of movement or migration. Stable isotope analyses of carbon, nitrogen, sulfur and strontium will offer further insight into what these individuals ate and whether they had moved during their lifetime. All these biological findings will be interpreted alongside archaeological, historical and cultural evidence to build a richer and more nuanced picture of daily life in the Roman city before the eruption of Vesuvius in 79 CE. Early tests indicate that the DNA is well preserved, making it possible to generate high-quality genomic data using state-of-the-art sequencing technologies. By comparing Pompeii's genomes with vast datasets of worldwide human genetic diversity, researchers will be able to trace the deeper ancestry and long-term connections of the population, extending from prehistory to the present day. Ultimately, the project hopes to make significant contributions to our understanding of Roman society, offering new knowledge not only to scholars but also to museum visitors, documentary producers and the general public. Its emphasis on the preservation and enhancement of cultural heritage promises meaningful cultural, scientific and social benefits at local, regional and national levels.

The experiences and the new protocols reported contribute to the needs of supporting the knowledge consolidation process with digital instruments and scientific methods, leading to the common goal of a better diagnostic investigation of organic material, and in particular for studying the biological and paleobiological materials and for assessing diagenetic processes.

Finanziato
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CULTURAL HERITAGE ACTIVE INNOVATION FOR NEXT-GEN SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY
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1. Introduction

The multi-analytical investigation of dental mineralized tissues has emerged as a powerful approach for reconstructing developmental trajectories and physiological events in past populations. When combined with microstructural analysis, the study of enamel provides direct evidence of early-life stress, physiological instability, and metabolic trajectories that cannot be captured through other skeletal markers. Yet, issues such as inter-individual variability, preservation constraints, and the complex aetiology of enamel defects require analytical designs capable of integrating complementary datasets. To overcome these challenges, workflows that merge classical histomorphometry with LA-ICP-MS trace-element profiling enhance the resolution at which enamel formation processes and stress episodes can be interpreted. On the other hand, coupling dental cementum microstructure with computational algorithms introduces a promising chance for refining adult age-at-death estimation in adult individuals, a longstanding limitation in bioarchaeological profiling. Together, these approaches expand the interpretative potential of dental tissues and contribute to more robust reconstructions of individual life histories.

Archaeological biomaterials such as bone, wood, and dental enamel are key sources of information for reconstructing past environments, behaviours, and evolutionary processes. However, their study is often constrained by significant analytical challenges. Burned bones, for instance, undergo profound chemical and structural alterations that hinder the detection of organic residues and complicate assessments of crystallinity; despite the availability of advanced spectroscopic tools, preliminary evaluations still rely largely on visual inspection of colour changes, a subjective and imprecise method. Wood poses similar limitations: radiocarbon dating, the most widely used technique for chronological reconstruction, can require the complete consumption of small or precious samples, and its accuracy depends strongly on the preservation of cellulose, which is frequently degraded under burial conditions. In the case of fossil teeth, although enamel is an exceptionally durable biomaterial, the organic fraction it contains is extremely small, making the investigation of amino acid preservation difficult and often dependent on destructive protocols. Likewise, the detection of amelogenins for sex determination traditionally relies on mass spectrometry, a powerful but costly, laboratory-bound, and sample-consuming technique. Across these domains, the reliance on invasive, destructive, or labour-intensive analytical approaches highlights an urgent need for rapid, reliable, and non-destructive methods capable of assessing the molecular preservation of archaeological materials while minimizing the loss of unique and irreplaceable specimens.

Recent advances in palaeogenomics and bioarchaeology have profoundly reshaped our understanding of ancient human populations, expanding the analytical scale from individual life trajectories to wider biological, social, and cultural dynamics. High-resolution genomic data, integrated with archaeological and anthropological evidence, now enable the

reconstruction of population histories, including migration patterns, admixture events, social interactions, and long-distance exchange networks. Palaeogenomic analyses of ancient human remains provide unprecedented insights into past communities, allowing the detailed reconstruction of phenotypic traits, kinship structures, disease profiles, dietary practices, mobility patterns, and overarching genetic ancestry from prehistory to the present. These developments have transformed our capacity to investigate both micro-level biographical information and macro-level demographic processes. Critical breakthroughs in DNA extraction, library preparation, and sequencing technologies have overcome many challenges associated with the degradation and limited preservation of ancient DNA. In parallel, sophisticated bioinformatic pipelines now permit the robust analysis of highly fragmented and damaged genomic material. For this project, minimally invasive sampling protocols will ensure the conservation of skeletal remains, while optimized extraction methods and next-generation sequencing workflows will maximize DNA recovery. Whole-genome sequencing will be employed to achieve medium-to-high genome-wide coverage (2–10×), enabling reliable population genetic and individual-level analyses.

2.1 UNIBO: Written within the teeth: high resolution microscopic analysis on mineralized dental tissues to reconstruct individuals' life histories and estimating the age-at-death.

2.1.1 Introduction

Dental remains constitute an exceptional source of information in biological anthropology owing to their remarkable preservation and resistance to diagenetic alterations. Their frequent recovery in archaeological contexts, coupled with the stability of mineralized dental structures, provides a long-term archive of biological, developmental, and environmental signals. Among these tissues, dental enamel is particularly valuable for reconstructing early-life histories. Enamel forms incrementally from the intra-uterine development through early adolescence and, unlike bone, does not remodel after formation. As a result, it preserves permanently a continuous and high-resolution record of developmental processes. Histological analysis of enamel allows the reconstruction of individual growth trajectories by investigating the incremental growth features within its microstructure and the developmental timing. When integrated with high-resolution chemical analyses, such as elemental or isotopic profiling, these data can reveal childhood shifts in diet, chemical imbalances related to physiological

stress events, and mobility [NLR20]. Because enamel formation in several tooth classes begins in utero, it also offers a rare framework for investigating maternal health, environmental exposure, and explore the mother-infant nexus during pregnancy [NLLCMB24]. However, enamel reflects only the earliest phase of life and provides no record of later development or adult information [H23].

In contrast, dental cementum represents a unique tissue among the mineralised components of the tooth, because unlike enamel and dentine, cementum continues to be deposited throughout the entire individual's lifespan [PGRQP22]. This thin layer covering the root surface plays a crucial role in anchoring the tooth within the alveolar bone when is subjected to masticatory efforts. In particular, the acellular extrinsic fibre cementum (AEFC) in the cervical third of the root exhibits a sequence of alternating light and dark incremental bands, observable in thin section under transmitted light microscopy in several mammals' species. Research on animal specimens has established that each pair of these annulations reflects annual cycles of deposition associated with seasonal physiological changes [YHYHA16]. Consequently, cementum analysis has been widely employed in zooarchaeology to determine season-at-death, providing insights into past hunting strategies and site-use exploitation patterns [LRRP22], [LRMP25].

The potential of cementum for estimating chronological age in humans was first proposed by Stott and colleagues in 1982 [SSL82], based on counting the number of annulation visible in the cementum of an individual. Age-at-death estimation is a key component of the anthropological biological profile, yet it remains one of the most challenging features that can be retrieved from skeletal remains [WF05]. Juvenile age assessment benefits from predictable patterns of skeletal and dental development, which allow highly accurate estimates. In adults, however, the cessation of growth shifts attention to degenerative skeletal changes and dental wear, even though these features are influenced by environmental, behavioural, and population-specific factors. These methods therefore tend to reflect biological rather than chronological age and are further limited by preservation and subjective scoring [WF05]. The search of more objective and reliable indicators has consequently turned renewed attention to dental cementum in the last decades.

Although numerous studies have reported generally good correlation between cementum annulation count and known age [WBGV04], accuracy tends to decline in older individuals and even still debated, it does not seem to be affected by pathological conditions. Moreover, most available approaches rely on manual counting, a process that is time-consuming, technically demanding, which requires the loss of a great amount of the sample, and vulnerable to both intra- and inter-observer error. Variation in tooth selection, region of analysis and operator experience can produce inconsistent results and limit reproducibility [NRG22].

In the present study addresses these issues through a dual approach. First, we conduct a histological and histochemical analysis of dental enamel from two individuals affected by a rare enamel defect, aiming to clarify the developmental processes underlying this pathology

to assess the potential microstructural alteration for interpreting atypical growth patterns. Second, and the core objective of our work, we develop and present a new semi-automated for cementum annulation counting based on a proprietary algorithm. This approach seeks to reduce operator bias, improve reproducibility, and enhance the accuracy of adult age-at-death estimation in anthropological contexts.

2.1.2 Results

Dental enamel. Histological analyses provided more precise timing of enamel defects than surface-based estimates. In both individuals the onset of the major hypoplastic defect lack of correspondence with additional defects in the dentition of the individuals, suggesting that this major plane-form enamel hypoplasia did not occur contemporaneously with other minor episodes, and indicating that could be the consequence of a localized event, such as a physical injury of the dentition during the development.

Despite the presence of hypoplastic defects and several Accentuated Lines, all the growth parameters fell within the range of variability of healthy teeth. In particular Daily Secretion Rate values remained stable and comparable with previously published healthy samples. No differences were observed near stress markers or along normal incremental markers. This lack of difference is also suggested by the topographic DSR maps (Fig. 1), which confirm a regular pattern of enamel deposition, indicating that the stress events responsible for Accentuated Lines and enamel hypoplasia did not alter secretion rates. Instead, these events likely affected ameloblast behaviour or crystallite organization rather than the daily rate of matrix production.

Figure 1. Topographic maps of Daily Secretion Rate (DSR) across the buccal surface of the crown in both sectioned teeth.

Elemental profiles show that Mg/Ca (Fig. 2) decrease sharply after the hypoplastic event and remain stable in areas without defects. This pattern suggests a localized disturbance in Mg homeostasis during amelogenesis. However, the restricted spatial distribution of the defects argues against systemic metabolism disorders. The enamel and elemental evidence more consistently point to a local traumatic impact, disrupting ameloblast activity in the developing permanent germs.

Figure 2. Elemental profiles from the teeth analysed. In green Mg profiles which show a sharp decreasing of the value after the hypoplastic defect (black line).

Dental cementum. Manual counts of cementum annulations in the DHOC sample showed inconsistent results across operators, although the intra-observer error was not statistically significant. The most accurate estimates relative to known age-at-death were produced by the operator with the greatest experience in cementum analysis. This supports the notion that manual age estimation from cementum is highly sensitivity to operator expertise and subjectivity, highlighting the need for less biased and more reproducible analytical approaches.

Application of the automated algorithm yielded a strong correlation between estimated and known ages, with a mean absolute error (MAE) of approximately 3 years. The MAE improved further when individuals with the lowest accuracy were excluded (Fig. 3). Notably, all four individuals with high underestimated ages showed pathological alterations or evidence of

structural impact in the cervical third of the root. This pattern indicates that cementum pathologies, such as alveolar resorption, directly affect the reliability of age estimates, underscoring the importance of careful sample selection.

Figure 3. Linear regression between automatic age-at-death estimation and known age ($y = 1.68 + 0.92x$). Pearson coefficient $r = 0.98$.

A second script developed to test the stability of parameter choices confirmed that the algorithm's performance is robust with only minimal variation between parameter sets. When compared with osteological age-at-death estimates, automatic annulation counts produced similar overall patterns but offered a distinct advantage: they provided single-point estimates rather than broad age ranges (typically 5-10 years) characteristic of traditional skeletal methods.

Application of the automatic counting method to the archaeological sample also produced precise age-at-death estimates. In cases affected by post-depositional alteration, the automatic method reduces the number of usable samples, whereas manual counting can be applied more broadly, though with the risk of misinterpreting post-depositional features as growth increments.

Among the five animal samples, accurate results were achieved for only two individuals. In most sections, annulations were not clearly visible, supporting the idea that cementum increment visibility reflects seasonal environmental variation. Since *Macaca mulatta* inhabits equatorial regions with limited seasonal changes, weak or absent annulation patterns are expected.

2.1.3 Materials and methods

Before any destructive procedure, all teeth were documented using either a Leica s9i stereomicroscope or a Hirox HX-100 digital microscope. Specimens intended for both enamel and cementum analysis were then processed following established protocols [EHG24]. Each tooth was coated with a reversible adhesive, allowing its removal from the resin block for potential restoration after sectioning. Teeth were subsequently embedded in a two-component epoxy resin and sectioned twice along predefined cutting planes using a diamond saw. From this point, the workflow diverged according to the tissue analysed.

Dental enamel. Enamel analyses focused on teeth exhibiting severe hypoplastic defects from two individuals recovered at Lazzaretto Vecchio (Venice, Italy). Each tooth was longitudinally sectioned along a plane parallel to the labio-palatal axis and passing through the dentine horn. Sections were ground and polished to approximately 150 μm thickness and examined under transmitted light microscopy to produce high-resolution composite micrographs of the entire crown.

Enamel growth parameters, such as Daily Secretion Rate (DSR), Enamel Extension Rate (EER), and Crown Formation Time (CFT), were quantified using standard histomorphometric procedures. Accentuated Lines, markers of physiological stress, were identified to reconstruct the developmental chronology associated with hypoplastic events.

The same thin sections were used for spatially resolved elemental analysis. Continuous laser-ablation profiles parallel to the enamel-dentine junction were acquired using LA-ICP-MS at the Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences (Krakow Research Centre). Data were calibrated using internal standards and NIST reference glasses [MNE19]. Elemental concentration profiles (Sr, Ba, Mg) were aligned with the odontochronological framework through LOESS (Local Regression Polynomial Fitting), enabling reconstruction of elemental variations throughout crown development. Sr and Ba were targeted to detect dietary shifts, while Mg was examined due to its role in enamel maturation and its potential involvement in pathologies associated with enamel hypoplasia.

Dental cementum. Cementum analysis was conducted on 30 teeth from known-age individuals from the Documented Human Osteological Collection (DHOC) of the Certosa Cemetery (University of Bologna). Individuals were selected to ensure equal representation of both sexes and distribution across five age categories (15-55 years), mitigating the possible age-related bias in older individuals documented in previous studies of manual counting.

The method was also applied to 5 *Macaca mulatta* specimens, analysed in longitudinal sections to test the methodological flexibility and on 30 archaeological human individuals from the Isola Sacra Roman necropolis (Rome, Italy), allowing comparison with traditional manual counting performed in previous studies.

Each DHOC tooth was transversely sectioned twice, perpendicular to the root surface, minimizing the risk of annulation-doubling artefacts [NRG22]. Using high-resolution transmitted light microscopy, two Regions of Interest (ROIs) were selected per section. For each ROI, two images were captured at different focal planes, yielding eight micrographs per tooth.

Annulations were manually counted by three operators with differing expertise. Micrographs were imported into ImageJ Fiji software, straightened for horizontal alignment of annulations, and processed with a Gaussian filter to reduce background noise. To enhance annulation visibility, a shadow filter (3x3 convolution kernel simulating directional illumination) was applied twice.

Cementum thickness was measured six times per image to compute tooth-level mean thickness. At least six clearly visible annulations per image were measured to determine mean annulation width. After conversion to pixel units based on camera resolution, this width was used to define a threshold parameter for distinguishing true from false peaks. For each image, 15-line profiles across cementum thickness were extracted, recording grey value variation along the thickness expressed in pixels.

A proprietary algorithm was developed in R software. Line-profile data were imported, and peaks were detected using the *findpeaks* function from the *gsignal* package [B21] and using the median of the annulation width as minimum peak distance to discriminate peaks. Descriptive statistics (median, mode, mean, SD) were calculated hierarchically at the line plot, image, ROI, and tooth levels. The median was selected as annulation count due to its reduced sensitivity to outliers and skewed distributions. The median of annulation count was added to the estimated age of root formation to calculate age-at-death.

A second algorithm assessed result stability by probabilistically selecting the minimum-distance-between-peaks parameter across the distribution of annulation widths for each tooth. A 10,000-iteration Monte Carlo chain was run; in each iteration, the median peak count was stored. The final annulation count for each tooth was taken as the median of all iteration-level medians.

The semi-automated script was also applied to animal specimens and archaeological human individuals. For both archaeological and DHOC individuals, age-at-death estimates derived from cementum analysis were compared with traditional osteological estimates to evaluate the method's performance [WF05].

2.1.4 Conclusions

This study highlights the methodological advantages of combining high-resolution dental histology, elemental profiling, and semi-automated computational analysis. Enamel microstructure and chemistry allowed a precise reconstruction of developmental timing, showing that even in the presence of defects, growth parameters remain reliable indicators

of early-life processes and expand the knowledge of ameloblast behaviour during specific disturbances.

The semi-automated cementum algorithm represents the main methodological contribution, offering a new method for the age-at-death estimation in anthropology. It substantially reduces operator bias, improves reproducibility, and yields age-at-death estimates with low error compared to manual counting. Its performance on archaeological samples further demonstrates its applicability to ancient remains.

Overall, this integrated approach strengthens the accuracy and consistency of dental tissue analyses and provides a more objective framework for reconstructing life histories in anthropological contexts.

2.1.5 Contributions

- Magri Stefano, Cerrito Paola, Nava Alessia, Bondioli Luca, Bortolini Eugenio, Sorrentino Rita, Belcastro Maria Giovanna, Benazzi Stefano. *Refining adult age-at-death estimation through semi-automated tooth cementum annulation (TCA) counting*. Contributo orale Congresso AAI (Associazione Antropologica Italiana) 2025, Cagliari, Italy.

- Magri Stefano, Higgins Owen Alexander, Figus Carla, Sassoni Enrico, Graziani Gabriela, Graziani Giulia, Philiotis Bryn Marie, Vazzana Antonino, Romandini Matteo, Anczkiewicz Robert, Mianowski Szymon, Bondioli Luca, Nava Alessia, Benazzi Stefano. *Early-life stress at the time of the plague: the case of two individuals with severe hypoplastic defects from Lazzaretto Vecchio (Venice)*. Manuscript in submission.

2.2 UNIBO: Development of Novel Analytical Methods for Organic Residue Recovery

2.2.1 Introduction

Burned bones. Ancient bones serve as valuable archives for reconstructing past life. However, identifying changes in organic content and the crystallinity of bone apatite following post-mortem alteration becomes increasingly difficult when burial conditions are combined with thermal degradation [LLC20],[SKS21],[WMR08]. Burnt remains are frequently excluded from advanced dating or molecular analyses due to their compromised structural integrity, yet in many archaeological contexts they represent the only available evidence. A detailed understanding of the chemical transformations affecting both the organic and inorganic components at each burning stage is therefore essential.

Preliminary assessments of burnt bones traditionally rely on visual inspection of colour

changes using reference charts as indicators of heat-induced transformations. Despite the extensive use of infrared spectroscopy in cultural heritage research, archaeologists still often depend on colour-based evaluations to infer burning phases. To address this, the Chemistry Department of the University of Bologna, in collaboration with the Bones Lab (DBC - Unibo) tested a cost-effective approach employing a portable FT-IR spectrometer (650–5500 cm^{-1}) and a miniaturised near-infrared (MicroNIR) spectrometer (900–1700 nm) on burnt bone samples, combined with multivariate data analysis to improve spectral interpretation. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) highlighted spectral variations that enabled differentiation of specimens according to their chemical alterations.

Wood. As with bone, wood is a valuable material for reconstructing the past and was used to create a wide range of artifacts. However, radiocarbon dating can completely consume the sampled material, and because cellulose is the preferred target in pretreatment protocols, its degradation poses challenges for both its extraction and the reliability of the resulting ^{14}C dates [CFK21]. This underscores the need for rapid, reliable, and non-invasive methods to evaluate cellulose preservation prior to sampling.

Building on recent applications of hyperspectral imaging (HSI) for collagen mapping in bone [LSO21], [MSO23], the Chemistry Department of the University of Bologna, in collaboration with the Bravho Lab (Unibo), assesses the potential of IRIS, a SWIR (1100–2500 nm) hyperspectral instrument developed by Bruker Nano Analytics, to qualitatively evaluate cellulose preservation in archaeological wood before radiocarbon analysis. IRIS enables rapid, non-destructive scanning of entire samples and can also be used in situ. Moreover, the SWIR range, characterized by lower absorption coefficients, allows deeper penetration and provides molecular information representative of the bulk rather than just the surface. Hyperspectral acquisition was paired with chemometric analysis, which uses multivariate statistical methods to extract chemical information from complex spectra, enabling the identification of cellulose-related spectral features and their spatial distribution through single-peak mapping.

Amino acids in fossil teeth. On the other side teeth enamel is a highly mineralized tissue mainly constituted by hydroxylapatite ($\approx 96\%$), water ($\approx 3\%$) and organic matter ($\approx 1\%$) [BSS19], [LHW17]. As enamel matures, its mineral content increases dramatically, from $\approx 15\text{--}25\%$ to over 95% by weight, while porosity decreases. This densification, particularly in inner and mid-enamel regions that mineralize earlier than the outer layer, results in a densely packed hydroxylapatite structure that isolates intra-crystalline organic residues [BCS19], [BPS21]. The organic fraction includes mainly proteins and proteinases, such as amelogenin, ameloblastin, enamelin and metalloproteins. Despite the low abundance of organic matter ($\approx 1\%$) in enamel, peptides have been found in fossil teeth that are several million years old ($\approx 24\text{ Ma}$) [GUM25], [PMC24], protected by the hydroxylapatite crystals. Although amino acid preservation has been extensively investigated in certain archaeological materials, such as mollusk shells and corals, it remains comparatively understudied in enamel. Analysing total

hydrolysable amino acids (THAAs) offers a means of estimating the full amino acid pool, encompassing both free and peptide-bound AAs, without requiring large sample sizes or highly destructive procedures. For this reason, the Chemistry Department of the University of Bologna, in collaboration with the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry (Mainz, Germany), systematically examined the temporal preservation of THAAs in fossil enamel as a proxy for evaluating the overall preservation of intra-crystalline organic matter.

Amelogenin detection. Amelogenins (AMGs) are proteins that play a central role in enamel formation (amelogenesis), as well as in cellular differentiation and tissue repair. In humans, the genes encoding AMGs are located on both the X and Y chromosomes, and the resulting sex-specific isoforms are widely used in forensic and archaeological contexts to determine the sex of skeletal remains [LCM24]. AMGs are usually identified by Mass Spectrometry (MS) [SGG17], yet this method has not been adapted to fast, low-cost platforms that offer miniaturization, long shelf-life, and minimal sample preparation. In this context, the Chemistry Department of Unibo in collaboration with the group of Prof. Simona Scarano (Department of Chemistry, University of Florence) propose the use of biosensors combined with next-generation bioinspired receptors, specifically molecularly imprinted soft polymers derived from endogenous neurotransmitters such as polynorepinephrine (PNE).

2.2.2 Results

Burned bones. Analyses performed on modern bovine femur standards, burnt at known burning conditions (S1 to S17), allowed the correlation of spectral features with seven different burning stages (BS0 to BS6). Portable FTIR was more effective for characterizing high burning stages ($BS \geq 5$). These stages were identified by the degradation and loss of the organic fraction (e.g., Amide I and II signals lost above 600 °C) and the appearance of specific degradation products, such as cyanate (NCO^-) and cyanamide (NCN^{2-}) bands (2000–2200 cm^{-1}). High burning stages also showed significant mineralogical changes, including the shift and bifurcation of the phosphate peak. MicroNIR, due to its deeper penetration depth, was better at distinguishing different stages below 900 °C ($BS < 5$), where organic materials were still present.

The integrated approach was applied to fifteen Roman-age burnt bone samples from Mutina (M1 to M15). The traditional visual examination, based on color, provided ambiguous results, often yielding broad temperature ranges and failing to distinguish samples effectively based on their preservation state. PCA performed on the FTIR data allowed to identify the specimen more degraded from the one better preserved.

PCA performed on the MicroNIR spectra of the better-preserved samples ($BS < 5$) successfully clustered the samples according to their conservation state. The analysis revealed that M3, M4, and M8 showed high levels of organic substances (CH and NH 2nd overtones) and were classified in the highest conservation states, intermediate between BS0 and BS1.

The integrated use of portable FTIR and MicroNIR, combined with chemometrics (PCA), proved to be a more rigorous and objective method than visual assessment for evaluating thermal alteration. This information is extremely useful as prescreening to identify the most suitable specimen to be sampled for further micro-destructive investigation which are based on the presence of organic substance such as dating or Zooms.

Wood. SWIR spectra of 35 archaeological wood samples whose cellulose content was quantified and was from 1100 to 2500 nm. was compared with pure cellulose and lignin standards. Key absorption bands attributed to cellulose were identified at approximately 1758 nm (C–H stretching overtone), 2048 nm (O–H stretching and C–H deformation combination band), and 2318 nm (C–H stretching and deformation). Bands characteristic of lignin were found around 1658 nm (aromatic skeletal vibration), 2122 nm (C–H stretching and C=C stretching), and 2376 nm (C–H deformation overtone). The samples with the highest cellulose yield exhibited spectral profiles that most closely matched the pure cellulose standard, while the samples with the lowest cellulose yield showed a predominance of lignin-associated bands, confirming that lignin is more resistant to degradation than cellulose.

Exploratory PCA was applied to the spectral data to analyze patterns based on preservation status. The first principal component (PC1) separated samples with high cellulose content from the ones with a lower cellulose preservation. This confirmed PCA as a rapid and useful qualitative tool for pre-selecting the most promising samples for ¹⁴C dating.

Hyperspectral mapping was used to visualize the spatial distribution of cellulose preservation within individual wood fragments. The distribution maps revealed that cellulose-related bands (e.g., at \approx 1760 nm) occurred in spatially opposite regions compared to those associated with lignin (e.g., at 1655–1671 nm). This inverse relationship highlights the heterogeneous nature of archaeological wood decay, where polysaccharides (cellulose) are preferentially decomposed, leading to relative lignin increase. Subsequent chemical extraction of α -cellulose using the standard protocol of the BRAVHO Lab confirmed the map predictions.

These findings validate the reliability of the NIR-based chemical maps to guide optimized, minimally destructive sampling strategies, thereby improving the overall reliability of radiocarbon dating while safeguarding cultural heritage materials

Amino acids in fossil teeth. The study compared modern and fossil enamel from three large mammal clades: Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, and Proboscidea; amino acids (AAs) were detected in all fossil teeth analyzed. The results indicate that while absolute AA concentrations initially decreased, AAs are nevertheless preserved well back into the Paleogene, at least up to 48 million years (Ma). AA concentrations strongly decreased during the first \approx 0.10 Ma (by about 55–96% compared to modern levels). This decline suggests that an initial, less protected organic fraction is lost from the enamel during early fossilization. After this rapid initial decline, AA concentrations stabilizes. The Late Pleistocene (\approx 0.125 Ma) is identified as the turning point when initial AA deterioration stabilizes. From the Late Pleistocene to the Eocene, fossil

mammal enamel AA content and relative abundance remain similar. According to the results obtained, the geological age is more important than the taphonomic setting (e.g., fluvial, limnic, coal seam) in determining AA stability over time.

AAs in modern enamel did not show significant inter- and intra-taxon differences in their distribution, indicating that phylogeny does not strongly influence tooth enamel AA composition. Equidae enamel may exhibit better AA preservation than the other taxa, potentially linked to differences in biomineralization or a higher relative content of intra-crystalline organic matter. Equidae showed the lowest intra-taxon variance in AA abundance in both modern and fossil samples. Conversely, Proboscidea exhibited the highest intra-taxon variability in modern samples, likely related to their unique mineralization patterns, which may result in a lower overall degree of mineralization and higher susceptibility to protein degradation.

A Random Forest (RF) model was built to evaluate the potential of AA concentrations to predict sample age. In the global model, Phenylalanine (Phe), Tyrosine (Tyr), Arginine (Arg), and Isoleucine (Ile) emerged as the most influential predictors of sample age, suggesting they show the most consistent concentration shifts with increasing geological age across all three families.

The persistence of AAs up to 48 Ma confirms enamel's potential to provide valuable geochemical information about the past.

Amelogenin detection. Molecularly Imprinted Polynorepinephrine (MIPNE) was used to create biomimetic receptors capable firstly of detecting full-length AMGs in standard solutions. MIPNEs were produced using a short synthetic peptide, selected *in silico* from the AMGX amino-acid sequence, as a template to generate highly specific recognition sites that mimic antibody–antigen interactions while offering advantages such as low cost, reusability, and environmental sustainability. Then, a “Finger-Imprint” (FI) strategy was introduced by employing the entire enamel protein extract as the template. This approach made it possible to tackle analytical challenges associated with complex and intrinsically heterogeneous matrices like dental enamel. The extraction method uses a digestion-free extraction protocol directly applied on enamel standard and allows the entire extract to be imprinted, producing receptors naturally matching the sample’s biochemical composition. The workflow is simple, fast, low-cost, and relies on biocompatible and biodegradable reagents.

FI biomimetic receptor was directly synthesized on bare gold Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) chips to assess imprinting efficiency and to characterise kinetic rates and binding affinities toward the standard protein. Finally, to meet the need for simple, high-throughput analytical systems, the FI protocol was adapted for use with Bio-Layer Interferometry (BLI). The BLI sensor comprises an optical fiber with an internal reference layer at the end and an external biocompatible layer where biological receptors are immobilised and exposed to the sample solution. FI-PNE receptors were synthesized on BLI tips by immersion in a polymerization solution consisting of the functional monomer and enamel extract.

Tips successfully captured specific binding cavities imprinted by AMG fragments from enamel, showing efficient binding toward standard AMGX and yielding significantly different signals when tested against real enamel extracts compared to buffer and control peptides.

The binding data were examined using t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), an unsupervised machine-learning method used to uncover hidden clustering patterns. The analysis showed that the standard targets produced uniform recognition profiles, consistently grouping together. In addition, responses from the human enamel extracts formed a distinct cluster clearly separated from both blank and negative controls, demonstrating specific and authentic receptor–target interactions. When the data were mapped according to donor sex, the t-SNE projection also revealed a partial spatial separation between male and female sample clusters.

This result provides encouraging preliminary evidence that the receptors can capture subtle, sex-related differences in the binding profiles.

In conclusion, the strategy successfully adapted the complexity of degraded proteins in real enamel extracts to pattern analysis via biosensing, demonstrating enhanced selectivity and capacity, and opening new perspectives for biomolecular differentiation based on complex binding signatures

2.2.3 Methodology

Burned bones. Regarding the evaluation of collagen preservation in burned bones, Unibo analyzed 17 standard burned samples with a portable FTIR spectrometer (Agilent Technologies) working in the 4000-600 cm^{-1} range, and a miniaturized NIR spectrometer (VIAVI solutions) working in the 900-1700 nm range. The spectra were corrected and the characteristic features of each stage of burning were explored. Then the pre-processed data were then subjected to Principal Component Analysis (PCA), an unsupervised method that enables data exploration and identification of trends. After defining the standard references, 15 archaeological samples were investigated with the same approaches.

Wood. Regarding the wood investigation, 35 archaeological wood samples from diverse geographical and chronological contexts, spanning approximately 300 to >50,000 years ago were analyzed. From these specimens, 43 subsamples were obtained to construct a quantitative reference dataset for chemometric analysis. Based on cellulose content, the fragments were classified into five preservation groups: A = <5%; B = 5–10%; C = 10–25%; D = 25–35%; E = >35%. For the 43 reference samples, spectroscopic analyses were carried out on the same fragments subsequently used for cellulose extraction, allowing for a direct correlation between spectral and quantitative data. The collected data were pre-processed and then subjected to PCA. Maps data processing also involved the creation of single-band

maps, in which the spatial distribution of characteristic absorption peaks associated with cellulose and lignin was visualized.

Amino acids in fossil teeth. Within the AAs research, powder from mature enamel from different modern and fossil tooth samples has been sampled from different museum collections. The analyses were performed in the laboratories of the Organic Isotope Geochemistry Group of the Department of Climate Geochemistry at the MPIC in Mainz, Germany. Prior to AA analysis, enamel powder was cleaned following an oxidative cleaning step able to isolate the intra-crystalline biomolecules but avoiding heating [DLP18]. For the determination of total hydrolysable amino acids (THAA) we used the methods proposed by Dickinson et al. 2019 [DLP18], with minor modifications. The analyses were performed using an Agilent AdvanceBio AAA LC Column 4.6 x 100 mm, 2.7 m 655950-802 and a Diode Array Detector (DAD). Standard in-house solutions of mixed amino acids (AAs) were prepared in known concentrations for calibration curves in order to quantify the AAs in real samples.

Amelogenin detection. The study used donated teeth, originally extracted for clinical reasons. LC-MS/MS analyses were performed using an Orbitrap Q Exactive plus mass spectrometer coupled to an HPLC microfluidic system U3000 RSLC (ThermoFisher Scientific), following a published protocol with minor modifications in order to characterize protein extracts. MIPNE receptors were synthesized directly on the sensor surfaces using two strategies: Single-Epitope Imprinting (SEI) and Finger-Imprinting (FI). The synthesis is intrinsically green, taking place in aqueous medium at room temperature without organic solvents. The Finger-Imprinting (FI) approach directly exploited the entire enamel protein extract as the template, creating a highly representative ensemble of binding cavities, unlike the conventional Single-Epitope Imprinting (SEI) strategy. These receptors were characterized using two label-free, real-time optical biosensing platforms: Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) for initial development and Bio-Layer Interferometry (BLI) for high-throughput analysis, which is advantageous for low sample volume requirements and reduced refractive index effects. The complex binding data acquired via BLI were interpreted using the unsupervised machine learning technique t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) to generate informative 2D visualizations.

2.2.4 Conclusions

Burned bones. These findings highlight how the integration of advanced spectroscopic techniques and chemometric methods in archaeological research represents a significant step toward more effective preservation strategies and more accurate assessments of ancient remains. The ability to perform rapid, non-invasive screening of bone materials increases the efficiency of conservation efforts and enhances the potential for further investigation of our

past. The results have been published in the Journal of Cultural Heritage.

Wood. This study highlights the potential of NIR imaging as a preliminary, non-destructive diagnostic method for evaluating cellulose preservation in archaeological wood, thereby improving the selection of samples for radiocarbon dating. These findings have been submitted to Radiocarbon.

Amino acids in fossil teeth. The results for total AAs in fossil enamel from Proboscidea, Rhinocerotidae, and Equidae show an initial rapid decline in amino acid concentrations within the first 0.10 Ma, followed by a period of stabilization. From the Late Pleistocene back to the Eocene, both the amino acid content and their relative abundances in fossil mammal enamel remain comparable, at least up to 48 Ma. These findings have been submitted to the Biochemical Journal.

Amelogenin detection. A novel strategy for creating biomimetic receptors using PNE was introduced to detect AMG-derived fragments in human teeth through a simple, rapid, and cost-effective protocol. A digestion-free extraction method was developed that requires only 1 mg of enamel powder, with the entire extract used directly for imprinting to produce receptors tailored to the sample's composition. The findings highlight the potential of MIBPs as stable and customizable alternatives to antibodies for rapid assays. The results have been published in Biosensors and Bioelectronics.

2.3 UNIFI (BIO): Paleogenomics: a tool for enhancing organic cultural heritage.

2.3.1 Introduction

Advances in genomics and bioarchaeology have expanded our ability to reconstruct history. Thanks to palaeogenomic and stable isotope analyses on ancient human remains, along with metaproteomic and metagenomic analyses of dental calculus, many features of individuals and populations can be inferred, as well as their genetic ancestry and legacy, integrating them into larger biological, social and cultural frameworks (migrations, admixture events, cultural and social interactions, commercial networks). Pompeii, the Roman city preserved under volcanic ash since the eruption of Mount Vesuvius in 79 CE, is a time capsule of the Roman antiquity and is part of UNESCO World Heritage List. The aim of this project is to reconstruct the living conditions and the social settings of this emblematic city of the Roman World.

2.3.2 Results

We have participated in several congresses and conferences to disseminate the results; we have published two other studies as reported in the two articles below:

Higgins O.A., Modi A., Cannariato C., Diroma M.A., Lugli F., Ricci S., Zaro V., Vai S., Vazzana A., Romandini M., Yu H., Boschin F., Magnone L., Rossini M., Di Domenico G., Baruffaldi F., Oxilia G., Bortolini E., Dellù E., Moroni A., Ronchitelli A., Talamo S., Müller W., Calattini M., Nava A., Posth C., Lari M., Bondioli L., Benazzi S., Caramelli D., (2024). *Life history and ancestry of the late Upper Palaeolithic infant from Grotta delle Mura, Italy*. Nature Comm., 15 (1), art. no. 8248. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-024-51150-x

PUBLICATION STAGE: Final

OPEN ACCESS: All Open Access; Gold Open Access; Green Open Access

Pilli E., Vai S., Moses V.C., Morelli S., Lari M., Modi A., Diroma M.A., Amoretti V., Zuchtriegel G., Osanna M., Kennett D.J., George R.J., Krigbaum J., Rohland N., Mallick S., Caramelli D., Reich D., Mittnik A., (2024). *Ancient DNA challenges prevailing interpretations of the Pompeii plaster casts*. Current Biology, 34 (22), pp. 5307 - 5318. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2024.10.007

PUBLICATION STAGE: Final

OPEN ACCESS: All Open Access; Green Open Access

Here we report the results of the others Pompeii individual:

The results of genomic analyses conducted on 173 sampled human skeletal remains are illustrated below. These analyses were carried out thanks to an agreement between the Department of Biology of the University of Florence and the Applied Research Laboratory of the Pompeii Archaeological Park, which involved the sampling of numerous human remains intended for the study of ancient DNA (aDNA). Regarding the human remains, the possibility of processing a large number of samples meant that genomic analyses could be performed only on individuals characterized by greater preservation of endogenous DNA molecules in the sample, thus achieving better resolution of the analyses and, consequently, of the final results. Initially, we carried out targeted sampling to obtain good powder (from bones or teeth), preserving the integrity of the find whenever possible. We then applied next-generation methodologies using NGS sequencing techniques to obtain information on the preservation of the genome of the sampled individuals. This work was performed both on individuals found in various parts of the city and on individuals belonging to specific and better-defined excavation contexts. For specific case studies, we performed deeper sequencing to reconstruct the complete genome at 1x coverage for individuals with an endogenous DNA quantity greater than 20%; whereas for individuals with lower endogenous

DNA, we used a target enrichment approach, which allows genomic information to be obtained even when the DNA is not well-preserved. In this way, it was possible to investigate, through genomic and anthropological approaches, specific dynamics that led to the formation of small groups of people, likely connected by affective bonds of various kinds, in sheltered parts of the city. Finally, all individuals with an endogenous percentage greater than or equal to 20% were used to conduct population analyses using a whole-genome approach. In this way, the genetic variability of the individuals who were in a dynamic and multicultural port city, as attested by the archaeological finds and documents discovered, such as the ancient city of Pompeii, was identified and compared with populations from different eras, located in various parts of the continent.

The sequencing at 5 million reads of the 169 libraries produced raw sequences whose analysis, performed using the EAGER v1.92.59 software [P16a], returned the main statistics reported in Table 1. The results obtained using the mapDamage v2.0 software [J13], which was employed to authenticate ancient DNA molecules through their characteristic degradation patterns, are shown in Table 2 and Figure 4. Table 1 reports, for each individual, the number of raw reads generated, the number of reads mapped after PCR-duplicate removal and quality filtering, the percentage of endogenous DNA, and the cluster factor (ratio between the number of reads before and after PCR-duplicate removal).

Table 1: main statistics related to the exploratory sequencing of the 150 processed samples. Individuals selected for deep-shotgun sequencing are highlighted in red.

ID Samples	Reads raw	Reads mapping	DNA endogenous (%)	Coverage medium	Cluster factor
Pom-1	17334740	1497783	27.768	0.0252	1.165
Pom-2	11768430	480247	13.072	0.0079	1.131
Pom-3	9216562	1468742	46.02	0.0254	1.002
Pom-4 /Pom-9	8914330	1829616	62.912	0.0295	1.002
Pom-5 /Pom-6	7909734	1487789	57.732	0.0237	1.002
Pom-7	7708392	148939	7.015	0.0018	1.002
Pom-8	17540314	11359	0.252	0.0002	1.154
Pom-10	15986928	23326	0.526	0.0004	1.153
Pom-10.1	16422876	3013625	63,151	0,0464	1.068
Pom-11	8733370	278	0.019	0	1
Pom-11.1	12131420	7563	1.754	0.0001	1.116
Pom-12	14105318	1486143	35.452	0.0259	1.145
Pom-13	6994790	2670	1.051	0	1.245
Pom-15	9989270	1913	2.435	0	1.064
Pom-16A	16980382	293664	9.125	0.0053	1.319
Pom-16B	15842786	238144	9.099	0.005	1.646
Pom-17	4596580	272	0.045	0	1.011
Pom-18	17632346	783	0.212	0	1.203
Pom-19	5381742	208716	9.293	0.0041	1.004
Pom-20	16939576	3166144	56.973	0.0526	1.2

Pom-21	31584038	1295350	12.746	0.0198	1.003
Pom-22	23499842	8587	0.473	0.0001	1.221
Pom-23	14557696	11546	4.489	0.0002	1.143
Pom-24	14664654	1071115	25.747	0.0156	1.104
Pom-25	12513118	968	2.674	0	1.257
Pom-26	11590940	2138653	59.253	0.0331	1.090
Pom-27	12035142	281362	8.95	0.0041	1.093
Pom-28	42887336	1280897	12.528	0.0191	1.098
Pom-29	14191600	6667	1.352	0.0001	1.092
Pom-30	12305416	2694582	73.81	0.0406	1.096
Pom-31	13830112	71408	2.472	0.001	1.110
Pom-32	10700412	1075558	36.911	0.0152	1.088
Pom-33	11465940	72633	2.163	0.0011	1.082
Pom-34	10424204	712	0.572	0	1.103
Pom-35	12732576	93449	2.345	0.0015	1.097
Pom-36	11409410	2565355	64.927	0.0405	1.099
Pom-37	8623328	1164378	36.49	0.0175	1.085
Pom-38	11446984	12605	0.653	0.0002	1.093
Pom-39	10710536	34014	1.317	0.0005	1.085
Pom-40	12665066	1890823	44.558	0.0292	1.095
Pom-41	14669830	2915042	57.652	0.0458	1.082
Pom-43	13170980	27152	1.446	0.0004	1.089
Pom-44	11199616	37804	1.413	0.0005	1.091
Pom-45	14185672	314918	7.596	0.0044	1.102
Pom-46	13888694	57695	3.234	0.0008	1.083
Pom-47	39712992	59386	0.649	0.0008	1.091
Pom-48	57686026	11009996	63.529	0.1699	1.094
Pom-49	51524626	6066	1.951	0.0001	1.286
Pom-50	50489070	843390	4.827	0.0136	1.102
Pom-51	46306698	183079	1.584	0.0027	1.099
Pom-52	48646526	3800	0.218	0	1.085
Pom-53	78956214	629746	2.75	0.0085	1.101
Pom-54	94439724	15322385	47.402	0.2633	1.112
Pom-55	44338156	303169	2.072	0.0046	1.096
Pom-56	57577900	7078821	45.215	0.1119	1.095
Pom-57	63361320	2117	0.255	0	1.119
Pom-58	57919990	109649	0.847	0.0015	1.09
Pom-59	31008314	2458	0.275	0	1.048
Pom-60	47488452	5848	1.102	0.0001	1.193
Pom-61	77114288	1394360	8.384	0.0203	1.093
Pom-62	53807276	17097941	88.253	0.2826	1.096
Pom-63	45524634	2291114	15.223	0.0351	1.099
Pom-64	64585610	6640361	33.014	0.1038	1.083
Pom-65	92268444	6677	2.739	0.0001	1.564
Pom-66	54190440	6108488	34.134	0.0938	1.086

Pom-67	54451340	446193	3.158	0.006	1.089
Pom-68	68164770	47371	0.606	0.0007	1.094
Pom-69	53032428	939169	4.991	0.0147	1.095
Pom-70	9415338	42084	2.329	0.0006	1.089
Pom-71	9641348	21007	1.195	0.0003	1.084
Pom-72	28323050	1349244	22.756	0.0196	1.098
Pom-73	9107130	106785	5.279	0.0018	1.085
Pom-74	16902258	6046	0.173	0.0001	1.079
Pom-75	12723178	434	0.031	0	1.101
Pom-76	12010472	113050	5.055	0.0017	1.094
Pom-77	12421892	2977461	94.274	0.05	1.091
Pom-78	47639490	3325941	28.391	0.0519	1.088
Pom-79	65033064	1720237	16.68	0.0271	1.088
Pom-80	24440610	831124	15.329	0.013	1.091
Pom-81	24383514	2796	0.078	0	1.099
Pom-82	11336616	30267	1.225	0.0005	1.095
Pom-83	12255478	2705	0.106	0	1.082
Pom-84	10583396	5792	0.282	0.0001	1.083
Pom-85	18360804	316614	10.854	0.0042	1.152
Pom-86	9694000	36703	1.825	0.0005	1.085
Pom-87	63915098	2041850	11.056	0.0324	1.091
Pom-88	13510586	2762788	80.422	0.0417	1.106
Pom-89	17511850	936	0.039	0	1.062
Pom-90	32985930	2485058	32.596	0.037	1.082
Pom-91	9367612	22294	1.376	0.0003	1.091
Pom-92	16280860	436	0.035	0	1.188
Pom-93	14217864	469	0.034	0	1.102
Pom-96B	25816846	2551546	30.217	0.044	1.121
Pom-98	30332192	3653	0.625	0.0001	1.063
Pom-99	32414444	610501	6.553	0.0086	1.114
Pom-100	28320056	1531729	16.466	0.023	1.103
Pom-101	19441518	831102	13.58	0.0125	1.103
Pom-102	25662206	243631	3.572	0.0037	1.11
Pom-103	18742766	2638519	40.943	0.0403	1.116
Pom-104	25714800	2823963	32.039	0.0456	1.109
Pom-105	14792338	5283816	95.14	0.0894	1.124
Pom-106	16123890	1489629	29.141	0.0228	1.103
Pom-107	16750040	5022464	93.065	0.0798	1.107
Pom-108	12925002	393006	8.114	0.0062	1.1
Pom-109	18456868	20744	0.846	0.0003	1.095
Pom-110	18823670	1785076	28.647	0.0254	1.1
Pom-111	14448664	743047	15.251	0.0116	1.096
Pom-112	15775090	1573613	29.961	0.0241	1.101
Pom-113	44710218	4076683	27.388	0.0651	1.122
Pom-114	21706264	247314	3.928	0.0038	1.112

Pom-115	19075872	60050	1.421	0.0009	1.107
Pom-116	15486616	25655	0.859	0.0004	1.119
Pom-117	19928620	1018687	17.726	0.0146	1.108
Pom-118	19023456	6053789	91.8	0.1006	1.116
Pom-119	21250038	60273	2.439	0.0009	1.111
Pom-120	45037942	200546	2.042	0.0031	1.128
Pom-121	15453040	876064	17.709	0.0127	1.111
Pom-122	20057744	1554647	24.395	0.0242	1.129
Pom-123	23160800	5183246	63.048	0.0842	1.114
Pom-124	39458138	11721614	94.769	0.1817	1.11
Pom-125	19251600	2873361	50.227	0.0498	1.147
Pom-126	15694056	2085721	39.791	0.0327	1.103
Pom-127	11874886	2544574	81.948	0.0351	1.174
Pom-128	17018716	3176361	73.981	0.0535	1.189
Pom-129	7899384	1317797	50.526	0.0213	1.039
Pom-130	8766362	33646	2.302	0.0005	1.04
Pom-131	11729364	384652	10.598	0.0059	1.051
Pom-132	7377614	1493994	61.161	0.026	1.042
Pom-133	6039136	97495	5.077	0.0016	1.042
Pom-134	3081374	88239	8.483	0.0014	1.035
Pom-135	8661206	133448	5.93	0.0019	1.05
Pom-136	12368640	618208	17.86	0.0093	1.041
Pom-137	11321984	316806	9.01	0.0054	1.036
Pom-139	4955446	444589	27.178	0.0076	1.038
Pom-140	11151332	596625	19.928	0.0107	1.144
Pom-143	14324414	183621	7.498	0.0028	1.137
Pom-144	10318860	381735	13.093	0.0054	1.139
Pom-145	10952110	107821	10.216	0.0016	1.149
Pom-146	9885504	182230	12.149	0.0024	1.135
Pom-147	10463740	7089	5.586	0.0001	1.208
Pom-158	18006246	1212762	22.421	0.0187	1.123
Pom-159	16808038	1564109	32.124	0.0253	1.121
Pom-160	16880072	3537450	64.756	0.0618	1.104
Pom-161	26435022	4735259	58.602	0.0782	1.121
Pom-162	15037490	3831389	86.9	0.0594	1.129
Pom-163	11349740	169233	5.79	0.0026	1.121
Pom-164	17559342	66184	1.943	0.0012	1.118
Pom-165A	12671210	102128	7.323	0.0016	1.142
Pom-165B	20043694	400015	6.826	0.0068	1.115
Pom-166	15948184	384314	10.038	0.0059	1.107

The percentage of endogenous DNA (the fraction of reads mapping to the human reference genome relative to the total number of reads obtained after merging) was the parameter considered when selecting libraries to undergo a second deep-shotgun sequencing run, with

the aim of reaching an average coverage of 1×. Endogenous DNA values range from a minimum of 0.019% to a maximum of 95.14%. DNA preservation is therefore highly variable: 67% of samples show less than 20% endogenous DNA, while 33% of samples display preservation above 20%—excellent results considering the degraded nature of aDNA. All samples show a low number of PCR duplicates relative to the total number of unique reads mapping to the human reference genome, as demonstrated by the cluster factor value, which is close to 1, indicating high library complexity.

Table 4 reports, for each sample, the C→T and G→A transitions at the first nucleotide of the 5' and 3' ends of DNA molecules, respectively, as well as the average fragment size.

C→T percentages range from 0.77% (in Pom-93 due to the low percentage of endogenous DNA) to 27.67%, while G→A transitions vary from 2.4% to 26.1%. The incidence of misincorporations at both the 5' and 3' ends is consistent with the antiquity of the human remains and with the half-UDG treatment applied during library preparation. The average fragment size, between 30 and 62 base pairs, is also consistent with what is generally observed in aDNA samples.

Table 2: results obtained with MapDamage 2.0 on exploratory (light) shotgun data.

ID Sample	Deamination in 5'	Deamination in 3'	Average fragment size
Pom-1	0.1114	0.1084	47
Pom-2	0.1066	0.1048	45
Pom-3	0.0727	0.0714	48
Pom-4 /Pom-9	0.0642	0.0637	45
Pom-5 /Pom-6	0.0631	0.0612	44
Pom-7	0.1222	0.1261	37
Pom-8	0.0959	0.0906	46
Pom-10	0.0495	0.0471	51
Pom-10.1	0.0984	0.0958	45
Pom-11	0.0194	0.0476	31
Pom-11.1	0.068	0.065	43
Pom-12	0.1165	0.1065	48
Pom-13	0.0608	0.0633	47
Pom-15	0.149	0.1017	33
Pom-16A	0.1429	0.1397	52
Pom-16B	0.051	0.0495	62
Pom-17	0.038	0.0116	31
Pom-18	0.0283	0.0218	30
Pom-19	0.0439	0.0428	56
Pom-20	0.0927	0.078	51
Pom-21	0.1233	0.1238	45
Pom-22	0.0634	0.059	49
Pom-23	0.133	0.1346	39

Pom-24	0.1131	0.1076	43
Pom-25	0.0297	0.0351	35.5
Pom-26	0.0982	0.0896	47
Pom-27	0.1121	0.1052	43
Pom-28	0.1112	0.1009	44
Pom-29	0.1299	0.1178	41
Pom-30	0.0749	0.0704	45
Pom-31	0.0662	0.0613	42
Pom-32	0.1423	0.1384	41
Pom-33	0.1163	0.1161	45
Pom-34	0.0511	0.0569	39
Pom-35	0.0811	0.0715	51
Pom-36	0.105	0.0956	48
Pom-37	0.1402	0.1345	45
Pom-38	0.0945	0.0988	44
Pom-39	0.1282	0.1323	45
Pom-40	0.1024	0.0989	46
Pom-41	0.0845	0.0788	47
Pom-43	0.0925	0.0933	41
Pom-44	0.1402	0.1436	38
Pom-45	0.0669	0.0665	41
Pom-46	0.1074	0.1019	42
Pom-47	0.1463	0.1434	39
Pom-48	0.0662	0.0613	47
Pom-49	0.0371	0.0709	37
Pom-50	0.0978	0.0869	50
Pom-51	0.1178	0.1125	44
Pom-52	0.0574	0.0538	38
Pom-53	0.1017	0.1002	39
Pom-54	0.0624	0.0472	51
Pom-55	0.0929	0.0862	46
Pom-56	0.1027	0.0906	48
Pom-57	0.0419	0.0263	31
Pom-58	0.2092	0.2039	41
Pom-59	0.0732	0.0679	42
Pom-60	0.0141	0.0237	40
Pom-61	0.1027	0.0952	43
Pom-62	0.0624	0.0545	51
Pom-63	0.1267	0.1181	46
Pom-64	0.0725	0.0672	47
Pom-65	0.0227	0.0464	36
Pom-66	0.1001	0.0937	46
Pom-67	0.1403	0.1386	39
Pom-68	0.0987	0.1045	41
Pom-69	0.1008	0.0954	47

Pom-70	0.1367	0.1281	41
Pom-71	0.1365	0.1258	39
Pom-72	0.1175	0.116	42
Pom-73	0.1286	0.1232	48
Pom-74	0.1287	0.1081	41
Pom-75	0.0388	0.0238	30
Pom-76	0.1423	0.1418	44
Pom-77	0.0766	0.0746	49
Pom-78	0.139	0.1363	45
Pom-79	0.0787	0.081	46
Pom-80	0.1194	0.1183	45
Pom-81	0.2767	0.261	42
Pom-82	0.1033	0.104	43
Pom-83	0.1895	0.1544	39
Pom-84	0.0936	0.0935	40
Pom-85	0.1337	0.1269	39
Pom-86	0.1393	0.1402	41
Pom-87	0.0687	0.0689	46
Pom-88	0.0467	0.0462	43
Pom-89	0.023	0.0405	31
Pom-90	0.0988	0.0972	43
Pom-91	0.1075	0.1072	36
Pom-92	0.0179	0.0167	31
Pom-93	0.0077	0	31
Pom-96B	0.1365	0.1348	50
Pom-98	0.0712	0.0562	41
Pom-99	0.1587	0.1527	41
Pom-100	0.1343	0.1283	45
Pom-101	0.1235	0.1187	44
Pom-102	0.0745	0.072	47
Pom-103	0.1171	0.1111	46
Pom-104	0.1131	0.1069	50
Pom-105	0.0517	0.0401	51
Pom-106	0.12	0.1169	46
Pom-107	0.0803	0.0728	49
Pom-108	0.1354	0.1226	48
Pom-109	0.13	0.1225	40
Pom-110	0.1394	0.1339	41
Pom-111	0.0955	0.0905	47
Pom-112	0.1076	0.1007	46
Pom-113	0.1111	0.1003	49
Pom-114	0.1233	0.1164	46
Pom-115	0.0809	0.0782	45
Pom-116	0.1101	0.1019	45
Pom-117	0.1286	0.1251	42

Pom-118	0.0848	0.0727	51
Pom-119	0.101	0.0981	43
Pom-120	0.0668	0.0613	47
Pom-121	0.1341	0.1311	42
Pom-122	0.146	0.1448	45
Pom-123	0.0674	0.0603	51
Pom-124	0.099	0.0923	47
Pom-125	0.1099	0.1089	49
Pom-126	0.0712	0.0671	48
Pom-127	0.076	0.0655	40
Pom-128	0.0341	0.0307	47
Pom-129	0.0983	0.0956	46
Pom-130	0.0881	0.0901	45
Pom-131	0.0989	0.0959	44
Pom-132	0.0877	0.0886	48
Pom-133	0.085	0.082	46
Pom-134	0.1215	0.1166	45
Pom-135	0.1106	0.1043	40
Pom-136	0.115	0.1106	43
Pom-137	0.0678	0.0674	49
Pom-139	0.0824	0.0798	48
Pom-140	0.0296	0.0272	49
Pom-143	0.081	0.0711	44
Pom-144	0.1162	0.1077	42
Pom-145	0.0516	0.0422	42
Pom-146	0.1148	0.1013	39
Pom-147	0.0382	0.0324	40
Pom-158	0.0984	0.0983	45
Pom-159	0.1092	0.106	46
Pom-160	0.0958	0.0952	49
Pom-161	0.0675	0.0649	46
Pom-162	0.0994	0.0989	45
Pom-163	0.0868	0.0875	44
Pom-164	0.0418	0.0414	49
Pom-165A	0.0824	0.0693	45
Pom-165B	0.0661	0.0662	47
Pom-166	0.1368	0.1321	45

The four upper plots in Figure 4 show the frequency distribution of the four nucleotides (A, C, G, T) along the first 10 bp of DNA molecules at both the 5' and 3' ends. Inside the square brackets are the mean frequency values corresponding to the ancient sample reads, from the 5' end position (left bracket) to the 3' end position (right bracket), while the values outside the brackets correspond to the reference sequence. An increase in the frequency of T at the

5' end of ancient molecules and of A at the 3' end can be observed.

In the lower plot, the frequency of C→T transitions at the 5' end (in red) and G→A transitions at the 3' end (in blue) is shown for the first 25 bp. Once again, consistent with expectations for aDNA analysis and with the half-UDG library treatment—which repairs internal deaminations while leaving the last two terminal nucleotides damaged—an increased frequency of C→T and G→A substitutions is observed at the 5' and 3' ends, respectively.

Figure 4: Plot generated with the MapDamage v2.0 software showing the transitions detected at the 5' and 3' ends of DNA molecules for sample Pom-103. The four mini-plots at the top display the frequency of each nucleotide, while the bottom panel shows the percentage of C→T (in red) and G→A (in blue) transitions.

Sex Determination. For the samples subjected to the preliminary analysis for endogenous DNA evaluation, and possessing a non-zero average coverage, molecular sex identification was performed as described in the section “Materials and Methods” under sex determination. The results obtained are reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of molecular sex determination. Individuals highlighted in red are those whose sex was assigned with uncertainty due to low coverage. Table 5 reports, for each individual, the number of mapped reads (Nseq), the reads mapping to both sex chromosomes (NchrY + NchrX), the reads mapping to the Y chromosome (NchrY), the ratio between NchrY and NchrY + NchrX (R_y), the standard error (SE), and the 95% confidence interval (95% CI). For most individuals, it was possible to determine sex beyond any reasonable doubt, whereas in some cases the number of reads was insufficient to allow confident assignment (rows highlighted in red in Table 3). Genotyping and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) The genome of individuals whose average coverage, following the initial exploratory shotgun sequencing, was greater than zero was genotyped on two SNP arrays using a pseudo-haploid calling approach. The results relating to SNP coverage for each individual are reported in Table 6. Only the samples genotyped on the Human Origins (HO) panel and with at least 10,000 SNPs typed were used for the Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

ID samples	Nseqs	NchrY+NchrX	NchrY	R _y	SE	95% CI	assignment
Pom-1	1497783	38907	3231	0.083	0.0014	0.0803-0.0858	XY
Pom-2	480247	22561	79	0.0035	0.0004	0.0027-0.0043	XX
Pom-3	1468742	72507	227	0.0031	0.0002	0.0027-0.0035	XX
Pom-4/9	1829616	50461	4101	0.0813	0.0012	0.0789-0.0837	XY
Pom-5/6	1487789	72712	216	0.003	0.0002	0.0026-0.0034	XX
Pom-8	574393	21247	65	0.0031	0.0004	0.0023-0.0038	XX
Pom-10.1	120479430	5737272	3632	0.0006	0	0,0006-0,0007	XX
Pom-10	23326	1154	1	0.0009	0.0009	-0.0008-0.0026	XX
Pom-11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-11.1	179211	7319	25	0.0034	0.0007	0.0021-0.0048	XX
Pom-12	1486143	71623	276	0.0039	0.0002	0.0034-0.0043	XX
Pom-13	29567	948	172	0.1814	0.0125	0.1569-0.206	XY
Pom-15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-16A	293664	13609	88	0.0065	0.0007	0.0051-0.0078	XX
Pom-16B	238144	4260	18	0.0042	0.001	0.0023-0.0062	XX
Pom-17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-19	208716	10368	40	0.0039	0.0006	0.0027-0.0051	XX
Pom-20	3166144	148623	508	0.0034	0.0002	0.0031-0.0037	XX
Pom-21	8406258	271212	84026	0.3098	0.0009	0.3081-0.3116	XY
Pom-22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-23	11546	538	14	0.026	0.0069	0.0126-0.0395	XX but not XY
Pom-24	1071115	50176	195	0.0039	0.0003	0.0033-0.0044	XX
Pom-25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-26	2138653	58363	4747	0.0813	0.0011	0.0791-0.0836	XY
Pom-27	281362	7349	591	0.0804	0.0032	0.0742-0.0866	XY but not XX
Pom-28	1280897	60139	213	0.0035	0.0002	0.0031-0.004	XX
Pom-29	6667	245	1	0.0041	0.0041	-0.0039-0.0121	XX
Pom-30	2694582	125793	424	0.0034	0.0002	0.0031-0.0037	XX
Pom-31	71408	3359	17	0.0051	0.0012	0.0027-0.0075	XX
Pom-32	1075558	50633	210	0.0041	0.0003	0.0036-0.0047	XX

Pom-33	72633	3309	23	0.007	0.0014	0.0041-0.0098	XX
Pom-34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-35	93449	2443	193	0.079	0.0055	0.0683-0.0897	XY but not XX
Pom-36	2565355	124176	368	0.003	0.0002	0.0027-0.0033	XX
Pom-37	1164378	31958	2555	0.0799	0.0015	0.077-0.0829	XY
Pom-38	12605	329	33	0.1003	0.0166	0.0678-0.1328	XY but not XX
Pom-39	34014	836	67	0.0801	0.0094	0.0617-0.0985	XY but not XX

ID samples	Nseqs	NchrY+NchrX	NchrY	R _y	SE	95% CI	assignment
Pom-1	1497783	38907	3231	0.083	0.0014	0.0803-0.0858	XY
Pom-2	480247	22561	79	0.0035	0.0004	0.0027-0.0043	XX
Pom-3	1468742	72507	227	0.0031	0.0002	0.0027-0.0035	XX
Pom-4/9	1829616	50461	4101	0.0813	0.0012	0.0789-0.0837	XY
Pom-5/6	1487789	72712	216	0.003	0.0002	0.0026-0.0034	XX
Pom-8	574393	21247	65	0.0031	0.0004	0.0023-0.0038	XX
Pom-10.1	120479430	5737272	3632	0.0006	0	0.0006-0.0007	XX
Pom-10	23326	1154	1	0.0009	0.0009	-0.0008-0.0026	XX
Pom-11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-11.1	179211	7319	25	0.0034	0.0007	0.0021-0.0048	XX
Pom-12	1486143	71623	276	0.0039	0.0002	0.0034-0.0043	XX
Pom-13	29567	948	172	0.1814	0.0125	0.1569-0.206	XY
Pom-15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-16A	293664	13609	88	0.0065	0.0007	0.0051-0.0078	XX
Pom-16B	238144	4260	18	0.0042	0.001	0.0023-0.0062	XX
Pom-17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-19	208716	10368	40	0.0039	0.0006	0.0027-0.0051	XX
Pom-20	3166144	148623	508	0.0034	0.0002	0.0031-0.0037	XX
Pom-21	8406258	271212	84026	0.3098	0.0009	0.3081-0.3116	XY
Pom-22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-23	11546	538	14	0.026	0.0069	0.0126-0.0395	XX but not XY
Pom-24	1071115	50176	195	0.0039	0.0003	0.0033-0.0044	XX
Pom-25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-26	2138653	58363	4747	0.0813	0.0011	0.0791-0.0836	XY
Pom-27	281362	7349	591	0.0804	0.0032	0.0742-0.0866	XY but not XX
Pom-28	1280897	60139	213	0.0035	0.0002	0.0031-0.004	XX
Pom-29	6667	245	1	0.0041	0.0041	-0.0039-0.0121	XX
Pom-30	2694582	125793	424	0.0034	0.0002	0.0031-0.0037	XX
Pom-31	71408	3359	17	0.0051	0.0012	0.0027-0.0075	XX
Pom-32	1075558	50633	210	0.0041	0.0003	0.0036-0.0047	XX
Pom-33	72633	3309	23	0.007	0.0014	0.0041-0.0098	XX
Pom-34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-35	93449	2443	193	0.079	0.0055	0.0683-0.0897	XY but not XX
Pom-36	2565355	124176	368	0.003	0.0002	0.0027-0.0033	XX
Pom-37	1164378	31958	2555	0.0799	0.0015	0.077-0.0829	XY

Pom-38	12605	329	33	0.1003	0.0166	0.0678-0.1328	XY but not XX
Pom-39	34014	836	67	0.0801	0.0094	0.0617-0.0985	XY but not XX
Pom-40	1890823	48933	4024	0.0822	0.0012	0.0798-0.0847	XY
Pom-41	2915042	76449	6337	0.0829	0.001	0.0809-0.0848	XY
Pom-43	27152	1273	13	0.0102	0.0028	0.0047-0.0157	XX
Pom-44	37804	1046	66	0.0631	0.0075	0.0484-0.0778	XY but not XX
Pom-45	314918	15006	46	0.0031	0.0005	0.0022-0.0039	XX
Pom-46	57695	1474	116	0.0787	0.007	0.065-0.0924	XY but not XX
Pom-47	59386	1748	127	0.0727	0.0062	0.0605-0.0848	XY but not XX
Pom-48	11009996	518073	1737	0.0034	0.0001	0.0032-0.0035	XX
Pom-49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-50	843390	40364	137	0.0034	0.0003	0.0028-0.004	XX
Pom-51	183079	8346	42	0.005	0.0008	0.0035-0.0066	XX
Pom-52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-53	629746	30648	98	0.0032	0.0003	0.0026-0.0038	XX
Pom-54	15322385	426258	36558	0.0858	0.0004	0.0849-0.0866	XY
Pom-55	303169	8114	635	0.0783	0.003	0.0724-0.0841	XY but not XX
Pom-56	7078821	171757	14190	0.0826	0.0007	0.0813-0.0839	XY
Pom-57	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-58	109649	3089	229	0.0741	0.0047	0.0649-0.0834	with XY but not XX
Pom-59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-60	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-61	1394360	38083	3125	0.0821	0.0014	0.0793-0.0848	XY
Pom-62	17097941	807477	2553	0.0032	0.0001	0.003-0.0033	XX
Pom-63	2291114	64075	5328	0.0832	0.0011	0.081-0.0853	XY
Pom-64	6640361	180927	14861	0.0821	0.0006	0.0809-0.0834	XY
Pom-65	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-66	6108488	292987	987	0.0034	0.0001	0.0032-0.0036	XX
Pom-67	446193	11770	957	0.0813	0.0025	0.0764-0.0862	XY
Pom-68	47371	2116	15	0.0071	0.0018	0.0035-0.0107	XX
Pom-69	939169	44199	129	0.0029	0.0003	0.0024-0.0034	XX
Pom-70	42084	1112	80	0.0719	0.0077	0.0568-0.0871	XY but not XX
Pom-71	21007	465	33	0.071	0.0119	0.0476-0.0943	XY but not XX
Pom-72	1349244	34202	2808	0.0821	0.0015	0.0792-0.085	XY
Pom-73	106785	2765	238	0.0861	0.0053	0.0756-0.0965	XY
Pom-74	6046	342	7	0.0205	0.0077	0.0055-0.0355	XX but not XY
Pom-75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-76	113050	2997	252	0.0841	0.0051	0.0741-0.094	XY but not XX
Pom-77	2977461	77162	6331	0.082	0.001	0.0801-0.084	XY
Pom-78	3325941	154586	444	0.0029	0.0001	0.0026-0.0031	XX
Pom-79	1720237	46914	3823	0.0815	0.0013	0.079-0.084	XY
Pom-80	831124	37396	119	0.0032	0.0003	0.0026-0.0038	XX
Pom-81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-82	30267	1481	4	0.0027	0.0013	0.0001-0.0053	XX
Pom-83	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-84	5792	306	1	0.0033	0.0033	-0.0031-0.0097	XX
Pom-85	316614	8360	698	0.0835	0.003	0.0776-0.0894	XY
Pom-86	36703	1084	78	0.072	0.0078	0.0566-0.0873	XY but not XX
Pom-87	2041850	97550	302	0.0031	0.0002	0.0027-0.0034	XX
Pom-88	2762788	133674	396	0.003	0.0001	0.0027-0.0033	XX
Pom-89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-90	2485058	115974	392	0.0034	0.0002	0.003-0.0037	XX

Pom-91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-92	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-96B	2551546	119298	80	0.0007	0.0001	0.0005-0.0008	XX
Pom-98	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-99	610501	29056	88	0.003	0.0003	0.0024-0.0037	XX
Pom-100	1531729	40522	3300	0.0814	0.0014	0.0788-0.0841	XY
Pom-101	831102	21864	1777	0.0813	0.0018	0.0777-0.0849	XY
Pom-102	243631	11741	45	0.0038	0.0006	0.0027-0.005	XX
Pom-103	2638519	128562	394	0.0031	0.0002	0.0028-0.0034	XX
Pom-104	2823963	77395	6369	0.0823	0.001	0.0804-0.0842	XY
Pom-105	5283816,	251093	812	0.0032	0.0001	0.003-0.0035	XX
Pom-106	1489629	39192	3226	0.0823	0.0014	0.0796-0.085	XY
Pom-107	5022464	133157	10869	0.0816	0.0008	0.0802-0.0831	XY
Pom-108	393006	19222	47	0.0024	0.0004	0.0017-0.0031	XX
Pom-109	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-110	1785076	86314	286	0.0033	0.0002	0.0029-0.0037	XX
Pom-111	743047	19510	1607	0.0824	0.002	0.0785-0.0862	XY
Pom-112	1573613	74197	250	0.0034	0.0002	0.003-0.0038	XX
Pom-113	4076683	193188	598	0.0031	0.0001	0.0028-0.0033	XX
Pom-114	247314	6553	499	0.0761	0.0033	0.0697-0.0826	XY but not XX
Pom-115	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-116	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-117	1018687	48763	148	0.003	0.0002	0.0025-0.0035	XX
Pom-118	6053789	161663	13481	0.0834	0.0007	0.082-0.0847	XY
Pom-119	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pom-121	876064	23480	1866	0.0795	0.0018	0.076-0.0829	XY
Pom-122	1554647	41733	3199	0.0767	0.0013	0.0741-0.0792	XY but not XX
Pom-123	5183246	247962	705	0.0028	0.0001	0.0026-0.0031	XX
Pom-124	11721614	572806	1426	0.0025	0.0001	0.0024-0.0026	XX
Pom-125	2873361	132602	106	0.0008	0.0001	0.0006-0.001	XX
Pom-126	2085721	98214	343	0.0035	0.0002	0.0031-0.0039	XX
Pom-127	2544574	67975	5129	0.0755	0.001	0.0735-0.0774	XY but not XX
Pom-128	3176361	140208	93	0.0007	0.0001	0.0005-0.0008	XX
Pom-129	1317797	35503	2744	0.0773	0.0014	0.0745-0.0801	XY but not XX
Pom-130	33646	1522	1	0.0007	0.0007	-0.0006-0.0019	XX
Pom-131	384652	18729	16	0.0009	0.0002	0.0004-0.0013	XX
Pom-132	1493994	40139	3246	0.0809	0.0014	0.0782-0.0835	XY
Pom-133	97495	2655	208	0.0783	0.0052	0.0681-0.0886	XY but not XX
Pom-134	88239	2414	166	0.0688	0.0052	0.0587-0.0789	XY but not XX
Pom-135	133448	6411	6	0.0009	0.0004	0.0002-0.0017	XX
Pom-136	618208	16882	1343	0.0796	0.0021	0.0755-0.0836	XY
Pom-137	316806	8475	657	0.0775	0.0029	0.0718-0.0832	XY but not XX
Pom-139	444589	12206	907	0.0743	0.0024	0.0697-0.079	XY but not XX

Pom-140	596625	16507	1223	0.0741	0.002	0.0701-0.0781	XY but not XX
Pom-143	183621	4899	372	0.0759	0.0038	0.0685-0.0834	XY but not XX
Pom-144	381735	18197	11	0.0006	0.0002	0.0002-0.001	XX
Pom-145	107821	3010	192	0.0638	0.0045	0.0551-0.0725	NA
Pom-146	182230	8747	2	0.0002	0.0002	-0.0001-0.0005	XX
Pom-147	7089	339	5	0.0147	0.0065	0.0019-0.0276	XX but not XY
Pom-158	1212762	32551	2484	0.0763	0.0015	0.0734-0.0792	XY but not XX
Pom-159	1564109	74506	38	0.0005	0.0001	0.0003-0.0007	XX
Pom-160	3537450	94960	7222	0.0761	0.0009	0.0744-0.0777	XY but not XX
Pom-161	4735259	229255	125	0.0005	0	0.0004-0.0006	XX
Pom-162	3831389	185296	79	0.0004	0.0003-0.0005		XX
Pom-163	169233	8401	5	0.0006	0.0003	0.0001-0.0011	XX
Pom-164	66184	3228	0	0	0 0.0-0.0		consistent with XX
Pom-165A	102128	2738	182	0.0665	0.0048	0.0571-0.0758	XY but not XX
Pom-165B	400015	10987	834	0.0759	0.0025	0.071-0.0809	XY but not XX
Pom-166	384314	9062	684	0.0755	0.0028	0.07-0.0809	XY but not XX

Table 4: SNPs covered following genotyping performed on both the Human Origins panel (HO, 597,573 total SNPs) and on the 1240K panel (1,233,013 total SNPs). Individuals with fewer than 10,000 SNPs covered on the HO panel, and therefore not used for PCA, are highlighted in red.

ID samples	SNPs covered HO	SNPs covered 1240K	ID samples	SNPs covered HO	SNPs covered 1240K
Pom-1	20757	37736	Pom-28	15368	28639
Pom-2	6454	11943	Pom-29	66	110
Pom-3	19889	37719	Pom-30	32509	60017
Pom-4 /Pom-9	23879	44456	Pom-31	846	1588
Pom-5 /Pom-6	19043	35557	Pom-32	12348	22983
Pom-7	1583	2940	Pom-33	949	1704
Pom-8	64	112	Pom-34	-	-
Pom-10	114	260	Pom-35	1324	2381
Pom-10.1	71	136	Pom-36	30229	57613
Pom-11	-	-	Pom-37	13296	25336
Pom-11.1	80	154	Pom-38	158	294
Pom-12	20241	37659	Pom-39	433	778
Pom-13	-	-	Pom-40	24075	44535
Pom-15	-	-	Pom-41	37526	68780
Pom-16A	2019	4105	Pom-43	338	599
Pom-16B	693	1418	Pom-44	420	759
Pom-17	-	-	Pom-45	3873	7039
Pom-18	-	-	Pom-46	680	1268
Pom-19	3026	5824	Pom-47	610	1172
Pom-20	41189	75973	Pom-48	123331	229235
Pom-21	15411	29130	Pom-49	-	-
Pom-22	-	-	Pom-50	10353	19913
Pom-23	103	226	Pom-51	2290	4138
Pom-24	12286	23074	Pom-52	-	-
Pom-25	-	-	Pom-53	6808	12902
Pom-26	26338	49398	Pom-54	154115	300119
Pom-27	3463	6267	Pom-55	3936	7222

ID samples	SNPs covered HO	SNPs covered 1240K
Pom-56	84266	154448
Pom-57	-	-
Pom-58	1199	2308
Pom-59	-	-
Pom-60	-	-
Pom-61	17045	31328
Pom-62	185054	345389
Pom-63	27070	51542
Pom-64	79922	148941
Pom-65	-	-
Pom-66	68256	129886
Pom-67	5031	9482
Pom-68	576	1031
Pom-69	11267	21465
Pom-70	586	1046
Pom-71	259	456
Pom-72	16337	29907
Pom-73	1539	2858
Pom-74	70	134
Pom-75	-	-
Pom-76	1402	2621
Pom-77	39657	73557
Pom-78	40551	75362
Pom-79	21704	40584
Pom-80	10770	19908
Pom-81	-	-
Pom-82	338	655
Pom-83	-	-
Pom-84	50	99
Pom-85	3573	6578
Pom-86	421	815
Pom-87	25973	48456
Pom-88	32773	61752
Pom-89	-	-
Pom-90	27720	52006
Pom-91	-	-
Pom-92	-	-
Pom-93	-	-
Pom-96B	33746	62999
Pom-98	-	-
Pom-99	6849	12976
Pom-100	18811	34635
Pom-101	9626	18109
Pom-102	2877	5469
Pom-103	28752	55201
Pom-104	33882	64291
Pom-105	66460	123907
Pom-106	18571	34157

ID samples	SNPs covered HO	SNPs covered 1240K
Pom-107	61128	114030
Pom-108	4566	8843
Pom-109	-	-
Pom-110	19039	36246
Pom-111	9583	17720
Pom-112	18450	34632
Pom-113	47890	90294
Pom-114	3153	5812
Pom-115	-	-
Pom-116	-	-
Pom-117	11235	21482
Pom-118	76695	142131
Pom-119	-	-
Pom-120	-	-
Pom-121	9885	18648
Pom-122	18833	35740
Pom-123	62475	117258
Pom-124	124601	237313
Pom-125	38523	71540
Pom-126	26127	48281
Pom-127	26487	50417
Pom-128	37667	70419
Pom-129	17006	31771
Pom-130	435	797
Pom-131	4507	8613
Pom-132	20585	38267
Pom-133	1293	2442
Pom-134	1101	2039
Pom-135	1433	2744
Pom-136	7250	13606
Pom-137	4343	8068
Pom-139	6020	11579
Pom-140	8223	15674
Pom-143	2158	4037
Pom-144	4054	7840
Pom-145	1238	2370
Pom-146	1845	3555
Pom-147	58	127
Pom-158	14997	27863
Pom-159	19884	37644
Pom-160	47806	89706
Pom-161	59309	111915
Pom-162	43653	84419
Pom-163	1901	3715
Pom-164	920	1741
Pom-165A	1254	2376
Pom-165B	5338	10133
Pom-166	4950	8984

PCA provides an initial visualization of the genetic variability characterizing the examined population.

Figure 5 shows the PCA, in which present-day populations from Western Eurasia and North Africa—used to construct the genetic variability space—are shown in grey. PC1 and PC2 (accounting for 0.75% and 0.36% of the total variance, respectively) were used to plot the variability of ancient comparative individuals already published in the literature, represented by colored circles (individuals included in the HO v44.3 dataset plus additional samples released after the dataset publication: [S21], [P21], [A23], and the individuals recovered at Pompeii, indicated with diamonds).

Figure 5: principal Component Analysis generated from the genomic variability of 61 Western Eurasian populations genotyped on the HO panel, onto which the 62 individuals recovered at Pompeii and the ancient comparative samples were projected.

It is evident that the samples analyzed in this study exhibit extremely high genetic variability. In fact, they are distributed across all the clines of variability of the modern populations used to construct the PCA. Most individuals from Pompeii overlap with present-day populations of the central–eastern Mediterranean, but there are significant exceptions. Many of them deviate from the main variability cluster, aligning with present-day Western European populations and even shifting outside the Eurasian variability range (towards North African populations). Not only do the individuals from Pompeii differ from one another, but they also show greater

genetic variability than that observed in already published Imperial-period individuals sampled in Rome and its surrounding areas (Italy_Imperial in the legend). A comparison with ancient populations described in the literature shows that Pompeii individuals who fall outside the predominantly Imperial variability cluster and align with present-day Western European populations are genetically close to individuals from the Roman provinces in England (England_Roman), to Imperial-period French populations (France_Imperial), and to Iron Age Italians (Italy_IA).

Finally, individuals whose variability resembles that of present-day North African populations cluster near the Imperial-period populations of the Iberian Peninsula (Spain_Roman and Portugal_Imperial), in which an African genetic component has already been identified [O19], [A23].

Deep Shotgun. Following the initial exploratory shotgun sequencing, 12 individuals whose endogenous DNA percentage exceeded 20% were selected. The choice of libraries to undergo deep-shotgun sequencing also took into account the individuals' positions in the PCA (Figure 6). Individuals whose genetic variability falls within the range already identified in Italy during the Imperial period [A19], [P21], as well as others that deviate from it, were selected in order to explore in greater detail the remarkable diversity present in Pompeii before the city was destroyed. The individuals selected for this second sequencing were: Pom-20, Pom-41, Pom-77, Pom-78, Pom-88, Pom-104, Pom-105, Pom-107, Pom-110, Pom-112, Pom-123 and Pom-124. Data processing, following the pipeline described in section 3.4.2, produced complete genomes whose main statistics are reported in Table 5.

Table 5: Main statistics for the deep shotgun sequencing of the 12 selected libraries.

ID Samples	Reads raw	Reads mapping	DNA endogenous (%)	Coverage medium	Coverage 1X (%)
Pom-20	315355754	50766004	56.973	0.8706	49.16
Pom-41	288033346	48897952	57.652	0.7845	45.64
Pom-77	363934738	88954783	94.274	1.5575	64.03
Pom-78	1370152184	76826608	28.391	1.2313	58.82
Pom-88	301058704	68432735	80.422	1.1035	58.4
Pom-104	951325962	115240445	32.039	1.9348	72.58
Pom-105	156609976	50167463	95.14	1.0317	55.92
Pom-107	291849948	86132781	93.065	1.4587	64.85
Pom-110	741284158	79851240	28.647	1.1522	59.36
Pom-112	498860104	55159152	29.961	0.8988	52.69
Pom-123	301240532	68901177	63.048	1.2264	61.45
Pom-124	485597608	143060275	94.769	2.3355	75.95

Figure 6: principal Component Analysis, highlighting the 12 individuals selected for deep-shotgun sequencing.

An average coverage of 1× was achieved, and in some cases as much as ~76% of the genome was covered at least once. As shown in Table 8, all samples exhibit the typical damage patterns of ancient DNA molecules following the half-UDG treatment applied during library preparation.

Table 6: Deamination values for the 12 deep-shotgun individuals obtained using MapDamage v2.2.1.

ID Sample	Deamination in 5'	Deamination in 3'	Medium fragment size
Pom-20	0.0958	0.0936	54
Pom-41	0.0856	0.0834	50
Pom-77	0.0753	0.0736	55
Pom-78	0.1373	0.1344	50
Pom-88	0.0460	0.0452	50
Pom-104	0.116	0.1162	53
Pom-105	0.0554	0.0551	64
Pom-107	0.0818	0.0818	53
Pom-110	0.1406	0.1398	45
Pom-112	0.1131	0.1109	51
Pom-123	0.0703	0.0699	56
Pom-124	0.1016	0.1020	51

The application of the method described by [S12] to the 12 individuals under study, aimed at determining sex on a molecular basis, confirmed the results obtained from the exploratory data. The results using the new coverage levels are reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Results from deep-shotgun sequencing for sex determination. Nseq: number of mapped reads; NchrY+NchrX: reads mapping to both sex chromosomes; NchrY: reads mapping to the Y chromosome; Ry: ratio between NchrY and NchrY+NchrX; SE: standard error; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval.

ID Samples	NchrY+NchrX	NchrY	Ry	SE	95% IC	Assignment
Pom-20	2339300	1604	0.0007	0	0.0007-0.0007	XX
Pom-41	1266076	97948	0.0774	0.0002	0.0769-0.0778	XY
Pom-77	2288504	177368	0.0775	0.0002	0.0772-0.0779	XY
Pom-78	3543296	1886	0.0005	0	0.0005-0.0006	XX
Pom-88	3307350	1782	0.0005	0	0.0005-0.0006	XX
Pom-104	3148552	244359	0.0776	0.0002	0.0773-0.0779	XY
Pom-105	2401663	1579	0.0007	0	0.0006-0.0007	XX
Pom-107	2298589	176243	0.0767	0.0002	0.0763-0.077	XY
Pom-110	3869841	2132	0.0006	0	0.0005-0.0006	XX
Pom-112	2620534	1738	0.0007	0	0.0006-0.0007	XX
Pom-123	3330307	1861	0.0006	0	0.0005-0.0006	XX
Pom-124	7057296	3003	0.0004	0	0.0004-0.0004	XX

For the four male individuals, it was possible to assess nuclear contamination by estimating heterozygosity on the X chromosome. For each individual, the contamination estimates obtained are reported in Table 8, together with their standard error and the number of SNPs involved in the analysis. All samples show a negligible level of contamination, as it is below 0.5%.

Table 8: nuclear contamination estimates in male individuals.

ID Sample	X contamination \pm SE	SNPs X-chr
Pom-41	0.0032 \pm 0.0012	3327
Pom-77	0.0041 \pm 0.0008	8924
Pom-104	0.0053 \pm 0.0008	13666
Pom-107	0.0048 \pm 0.001	9055

In addition, for all individuals—both males and females—mitochondrial contamination was estimated as described in section 3.4.4. In this case as well, contamination values are negligible, as shown in Table 11, which also reports the number of reads mapping to the mitochondrion, the mean mitochondrial coverage, and the mt/nuclear ratio. By evaluating this latter parameter (< 200), and considering that the starting material for most individuals consisted of petrous bones, it is possible to extend the inference of negligible nuclear contamination also to female individuals, as suggested by [FRN18].

Table 9: mitochondrial DNA statistics and contamination estimates.

Sample ID	Reads on MT	Coverage MT	Contamination mtDNA	mt/nuc Ratio
Pom-20	22662	72.42	0.01 (0-0.2)	83.22
Pom-41	26646	81.09	0.01 (0-0.2)	103.43
Pom-77	31060	100.73	0.01 (0-0.2)	64.7
Pom-78	35908	109.69	0.01 (0-0.2)	89.3
Pom-88	28472	84.64	0.01 (0-0.2)	76.73
Pom-104	51369	165.9	0.01 (0-0.2)	85.78
Pom-105	16187	60.61	0.01 (0-0.2)	58.76
Pom-107	26077	83.85	0.01 (0-0.2)	57.5
Pom-110	38998	108.41	0.01 (0-0.2)	94.14
Pom-112	38031	116.74	0.01 (0-0.2)	129.97
Pom-123	27000	87.47	0.01 (0-0.2)	71.35
Pom-124	34127	104.24	0.01 (0-0.2)	44.64

Identification of Uniparental Haplogroups. The assignment of uniparental haplogroups (mtDNA and chrY) was successfully completed for all individuals analyzed. Table 12 reports, for the 12 individuals, the mitochondrial haplogroups with their associated quality values and the Y-chromosome haplogroups with the number of valid markers used for their identification.

Table 10: mitochondrial and Y-chromosome haplogroups identified in the 12 deep-shotgun individuals.

ID Sample	Haplogroup mtDNA	Quality	Haplogroup chrY	Valid Markers
Pom-20	H	0.82	-	-
Pom-41	J1c1	0.92	T1a1a	5438
Pom-77	H14a	0.95	J2a2a1a~	14382
Pom-78	HV0+195	0.97	-	-
Pom-88	H1e1b1	0.9	-	-
Pom-104	J1d1a	0.96	J2a1a1a2b2a1a1a~	19363
Pom-105	H1+16189	0.91	-	-
Pom-107	H14b	0.85	J2a1a1b3	13352
Pom-110	U5a1+@16192	0.97	-	-
Pom-112	H13b1+200	0.91	-	-
Pom-123	HV1a3a	0.93	-	-
Pom-124	H13a2b3	0.92	-	-

Three of the four male individuals possess Y-chromosome haplogroups belonging to the macro-haplogroup J2, already attested in the Iberian Peninsula during the Imperial period [O19] and associated with the presence of the Phoenicians [Z08]. Haplogroup T, on the other hand, is widely distributed across Europe, the Middle East, India, and the Horn of Africa. Although the Y-haplogroup of Pom-41 falls within this variability, it is also the only assignment

supported by a smaller number of valid markers.

The mtDNA haplogroups fall within the mitochondrial variability already observed in Europe. The macro-haplogroups HV, H, and J are the most widespread on the continent, first appearing after the last glaciation and increasing further in frequency following the Neolithic transition [P16b], [MV21]. Haplogroup U5, which appeared in the Late Paleolithic/Early Mesolithic and therefore arrived with HG groups from glacial refugia, is also very common in Europe [P16b], [MV21].

Genotyping and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The 12 individuals were genotyped once again using the HO SNP array with pseudo-haploid calling. Thanks to the deep-shotgun data, the number of SNPs genotyped is higher than that reported for the same individuals in Table 4. The updated coverage data are reported in Table 11.

Table 11: number of SNPs genotyped on the HO panel (597,573) in the deep-shotgun individuals.

ID sample	SNPs covered HO
Pom-20	402969
Pom-41	388860
Pom-77	503104
Pom-78	469156
Pom-88	458467
Pom-104	538985
Pom-105	441706
Pom-107	506519
Pom-110	454986
Pom-112	407613
Pom-123	475468
Pom-124	562097

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) constructed using the same modern populations applied in the PCA based on the light-shotgun data, and comparing the 12 Pompeii individuals with the same ancient populations available in the literature, yielded the results shown in Figure 7.

Although the overall arrangement of the genetic variability of the 12 individuals confirms what was observed using the exploratory shotgun data (Figure 6), some differences can be noted. In Figure 7, individuals overlapping with the variability of present-day central–western Mediterranean populations—together with contemporaries from the capital of the Empire and its surroundings—tend to cluster more closely with one another.

Supporting evidence for substantial genetic variability within the ancient city of Pompeii is provided by six individuals who continue to fall outside the primarily Imperial cluster, with one individual approaching even more closely the Imperial-period populations of the Iberian Peninsula, where a North African component has been documented [O19], [A23].

Figure 7: principal Component Analysis (PCA) generated from the genomic variability of 61 Western Eurasian and North African populations genotyped on the HO panel, onto which the 12 deep-shotgun individuals and the ancient comparative samples were projected.

Whole-Genome Approach. Statistics relating to the coverage of genomic sites read at least 1, 3, and 5 times in the 12 deep-shotgun individuals are reported in Table 12.

Table 12: Number of nucleotides read at least 1, 3, and 5 times in individuals with an average coverage of 1x.

ID sample	Coverage (bp)		
	≥1	≥3	≥5
Pom-20	1530616397	288297968	36582956
Pom-41	1424137020	245093341	30198522
Pom-77	1998914455	732685586	210577990
Pom-78	1836660074	522318521	103761361
Pom-88	1824625685	414155900	51136264
Pom-104	2270155220	1012763099	284961953
Pom-105	1743362699	367293224	44132592
Pom-107	2026821591	677301025	142291453
Pom-110	1854404896	450384623	61905186
Pom-112	1642838290	272796282	24977429
Pom-123	1918552939	498431068	70334864
Pom-124	2377500451	1294420641	458082297

The number of nucleotides shared among all 12 genomes examined (100% of individuals) was

calculated, as well as the number shared across progressively lower percentages of individuals, in order to maximize the number of positions covered and shared by as many individuals as possible. In addition, masks were applied to the genomic regions shared at the various percentages to ensure that subsequent analyses were conducted only on neutral regions, thereby avoiding biases caused by environmental adaptation. The number of base pairs shared among the different percentages of individuals, before and after applying the masks to the autosomal regions of the genome, is reported in Table 13.

Table 13: genome-wide and neutral-region coverage shared by different percentages of individuals.

Positions (bp) in various % of individuals	Coverage (bp)					
	≥1	≥3	≥5	≥1	≥3	≥5
	Without masks			With masks		
100% (12)	189948885	284487	41484	34701375	39885	-
90% (11)	553339875	1609193	78846	103616249	239023	-
80% (10)	977786808	6979737	130470	186592871	1100020	-
70% (8)	1716405601	62185602	437603	335531558	10616675	-
60% (7)	1980393317	139442504	1166927	389712885	24494957	-
50% (6)	2176490437	271941528	3842228	430002799	49039492	-
40% (5)	2315549317	474748885	13091769	458191248	87721669	-
30% (4)	2412368448	759088501	42032952	477212243	143452147	-
20% (2)	2530774922	1574920999	346262492	498275970	309289945	-

The subsequent analyses (PCA and Admixture) were performed by calculating genotype likelihoods (GL) limited to autosomal neutral and polymorphic positions (filtered with the parameter $-SNP_pval\ 1e-6$) that were covered at least once and shared among 80% of the individuals. Using only positions shared across the individuals under study ensures greater robustness in downstream analyses.

PCAngsd. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was carried out using the GLs of 783,840 positions (the result of filtering based on the data in Table 13), and included only a comparison of the 12 Pompeii individuals with ancient populations already published in the literature. Although only neutral positions shared among the Pompeii individuals were used, the whole-genome approach resulted in a higher number of SNPs than that of the HO panel (597,573 sites), which is typically used for similar analyses based on pseudo-haploid data.

The distribution of genomic variability along PC1 and PC2 (explaining 2.61% and 0.94% of the total variance, respectively) produced the results shown in Figure 8.

In Figure 8, the distribution of the ancient comparative populations is consistent with what has already emerged from the pseudo-haploid analyses of the same datasets. The comparison between these ancient populations and the individuals recovered at Pompeii leads to the following considerations: Most Pompeii individuals overlap with Imperial-period populations from Rome and its surroundings (Italy_Imperial). However, the Pompeii individuals show greater dispersion in the PCA compared to the more compact cluster

represented by Roman Imperial individuals (depicted as blue-colored dots).

Figure 8: principal Component Analysis (PCA) constructed from genotype likelihoods (GL) calculated for the Pompeii individuals and for ancient populations previously sequenced using a shotgun approach.

Pom-78, Pom-110, and Pom-112 fall outside the genetic variability characteristic of the Imperial cluster, positioning themselves near Italian Bronze Age and Iron Age populations (Italy_BA and Italy_IA). This proximity is particularly strong for Pom-110. Pom-78, instead, is located near individuals from the Roman provinces in England (England_Roman) and near French and Portuguese Imperial individuals (France_Imperial and Portugal_Imperial). Finally, Pom-112 appears to lie at the edge of the Italian Imperial variability, not far from French Imperial populations. A difference relative to the PCA based on pseudo-haploid data concerns Pom-41. Previously, this individual fell outside the Imperial cluster, close to present-day North African variability and to individuals from the Roman provinces of Spain (Spain_Roman), which do not appear in this analysis because they are capture-based genomes. The current position of Pom-41 (within Imperial variability) may therefore be due to the greater number of positions available for analysis thanks to the whole-genome approach.

Some individuals (Pom-77, Pom-104, Pom-107, Pom-124) still fall outside the Imperial variability, although they do not appear to cluster with any other ancient comparative populations.

NGSAdmix. To analyze the genomic diversity observed in the PCA in greater detail, an Admixture analysis was performed on all ancient individuals included in the dataset (selected according to the criteria described in the relevant section of "Materials and Methods"), this time including the ancestral populations as well. The analysis used genotype likelihoods (GL) calculated on 1,246,484 polymorphic autosomal positions.

Although the number of source populations tested in NgsAdmix ranged from 2 to 10 (–K2 to –K10), the plotted output corresponds to a model assuming that the Pompeii population derives from five ancestral groups (K = 5; Figure 9), as this representation allows clearer identification of patterns of variability among individuals and populations.

In Figure 9, each rectangle represents an individual belonging to the population indicated by the label. Each rectangle is composed of one or more colors, in different proportions, representing the genomic components maximized within that individual's DNA.

The Admixture analysis confirmed the variability patterns already identified through PCA.

Although the Neolithic ancestry of the first Anatolian farmers (Anatolia_N) is represented by the yellow component, in Italian Copper Age individuals (Italy_CA— a period in which genomes contain only Neolithic and

Western Hunter-Gatherer ancestry, with WHG shown in blue), the Neolithic ancestry is accompanied by an additional component (green), which is not maximized in any of the older individuals included in this analysis.

Figure 9: plot of the results obtained from the Admixture analysis with K = 5 (five source populations). On the left side of the plot are the ancestral populations, followed by the ancient populations used for comparison in chronological order, and finally the 12 deep-shotgun individuals from Pompeii.

The transition from the Copper Age (CA) to the Bronze Age (BA) is marked by the appearance, in the genomes of some individuals, of the component associated with the Steppe ancestry (shown in red). As already observed in the PCA (Figure 7), the analysis in Figure 8 also shows that the genetic structure present during the BA persists into the Italian Iron Age (IA).

Outside the Italian peninsula, the Imperial period is characterized by a strong presence of the Steppe component, especially in France and in the Roman provinces of England (France_Imperial, England_Roman), and to a lesser extent in Portugal (Portugal_Imperial). This pattern is also visible in the PCA (Figure 7), as all the above-mentioned populations cluster on the right side of the plot.

A clear shift in the genomic structure of the population within Italy occurs during the Imperial period. In Figure 9, individuals assigned to Italy_Imperial show a low presence of the Steppe ancestry and the appearance of a new genomic component traceable to Neolithic Iranian populations (Iran_N, shown in orange). Although this component is present to a lesser degree in a few foreign individuals, it increases significantly among the Italian individuals. This difference is accompanied by a shift in the PCA (Figure 8) toward the left side of the plot. What is observed in Pompeii through the Admixture analysis is a mixture of everything found not only in the same period outside the peninsula but also across different periods within the region.

Pom-41, Pom-88, and Pom-123 have profiles consistent with the genetic variability already identified among Italy_Imperial. Pom-104 and Pom-107 also appear to have typically Imperial ancestry, although unlike the former individuals, their position in the PCA is distant from the main Imperial cluster (they lack the WHG component).

Individuals Pom-105 and Pom-20, although genetically consistent with the Italian Imperial variability, show a Steppe component equal to or stronger than the Iranian Neolithic component. Indeed, in the PCA, although they remain within the variability of that period, they tend to align more closely with some France_Imperial individuals, which are known to carry a stronger Steppe contribution.

Pom-78 displays a distinctive profile, characterized by an absence of the Iran_N component and a genomic structure identical to individuals from the Roman provinces of England (England_Roman) and to French Imperial individuals (France_Imperial), as also suggested by the PCA in Figure 8.

In Pom-77 and Pom-124, the Anatolia_N and Iran_N components are maximized—an opposite pattern compared to Pom-110 and Pom-112, in which the orange component is entirely replaced by the red Steppe component. This is consistent with their PCA positions: Pom-110 and Pom-112 fall outside the Imperial cluster and resemble individuals from the Italian BA and IA. Interestingly, four outlier individuals from Figure 9 (Pom-77, Pom-104, Pom-107, Pom-124), although all positioned on the left side of the PCA, do not share homogeneous genomic profiles. However, a common characteristic among them is the complete or near-complete absence of the Steppe component, which instead is recurrent among individuals shifted to the right side of the PCA in Figure 8.

In the future, the analysis should be repeated with an expanded number of ancestral populations to better highlight differences within the genomes of the individuals studied.

The results obtained through genotype-likelihood-based analyses demonstrate that GLs represent a valid and statistically more robust alternative for performing genomic studies on ancient populations sequenced at low coverage.

The Room of the Skeletons. The extracts from samples Pom-1, Pom-2, Pom-3, Pom-4, Pom-5, Pom-6, Pom-7, Pom-8, Pom-9, Pom-10, Pom-11, and Pom-12 were quantified using the Quantifiler Trio kit, and the results are reported in Table 14.

Table 14: results obtained from the Quantifiler Trio kit analysis.

Campione	Large target pg/ul	Small target pg/ul	Y target pg/ul
POM1	ND	270	250
POM2	ND	130	ND
POM3	70	1000	ND
POM4	90	1028	1005
POM5	30	390	ND
POM6	ND	10	ND
POM7	ND	ND	ND
POM8	ND	ND	ND
POM9	ND	10	10
POM10	ND	20	ND
POM11	ND	ND	ND
POM12	10	250	ND

Subsequently, the extract from each sample—when necessary—was concentrated and subjected to amplification using a kit capable of co-analyzing 21 autosomal STRs, one Y-chromosome STR, Y-indels, and amelogenin for sex determination. The data obtained are reported in Table 15.

Once the profiles were generated, they were used to perform a blind search with the software Familias v.3 to evaluate kinship relationships among the analyzed individuals.

The analyses performed using a forensic approach (typing of Short Tandem Repeat loci) demonstrated, based on the 12 human remains analyzed, the presence of 10 individuals inside the “Room of the Skeletons” in the “House of the Garden” complex. Specifically, the human remains labeled Pom-4 and Pom-9 were found to belong to the same person, as were those of Pom-5 and Pom-6.

Anthropological analyses identified the presence of 4 adults and 6 subadults inside the room. Interestingly, despite the site having undergone disturbances over the centuries, the spatial distribution of the remains provides valuable information: the adults were found near the entrance, while the subadults were located at the back of the room.

The same samples analyzed with the forensic approach were enriched for the mitochondrial genome using the protocol of [MWP10]. For all samples, it was possible to reconstruct the complete mitogenome, with an average coverage ranging from 29.18 to 1327.36, and an average fragment length between 48.77 bp and 63.18 bp (Table 16).

Table 15: results of mtDNA and STR profiles.

Sample	mtDNA	D3S1358	vWA	D16S539	CSF1PO	TPOX	Amelogenina	D8S1179
POM1	T2b7a2	18-18	16-18	11-12			XY	12-16
POM2	H4a1a1a	18-18	18-18				XX	13-13
POM3	K1a2	15-17	15-18	12-13	10-13	11-11	XX	13-13
POM4	U7a	15-15	17-18	9-13	11-13	8-8	XY	10-15
POM5	I2	16-17	17-18	12-12	12-12	8-8	XX	12-13
POM6	I2	16-17	18-18	12-12			XX	12-12
POM 7	H9a						XY	
POM 8	K1a2							
POM9	U7a	15-15	17-18	13-13	13-13		XY	10-15
POM10	H7d3	14-16	14-16				XX	8-8
POM 11	H3a1							
POM12	I2	15-16	17-18	10-12	12-12		XX	13-14

Sample	D21S11	D18S51	DYS391	D2S411	D19S433	TH01	FGA	D22S1045
POM1	28-28	13-13		11-11	16-16	6-6	24-24	15-17
POM2	28-32.2			10-14	14-16	8-9.3	20-23	15-15
POM3	28-30	16-16		11-14	13-15	9-10	22-22	11-16
POM4	30-30	12-16	11	11-11	13-15	6-9.3	19-24	15-16
POM5	29-32.2	16-18		10-10	13-15	7-9	22-22	15-16
POM6	29-32.2			10-10	13-15		22-22	15-16
POM 7								
POM 8								
POM9	30-30	16-16		11-14	13-15	6-9.3	19-24	15-16
POM10	27-28			10-14	12-14	6-9		15-17
POM 11								
POM12	29-31.2	14-14		10-10	15-15	6-9	22-24	16-16

Sample	D13S317	D7S820	SE33	D10S1248	D1S1656	D12S291	D2S1338	D5S818
POM1	9-11			14-14	13-13	20-22		11-12
POM2	8-11	11-11	15-28.2	13-16	16-17	19-22		11-13
POM3	8-11	8-10	20-30.2	13-16	15-15	17-19	24-25	10-11
POM4	8-9	11-12	26.2-28.2	13-14	15-17.3	18-18	17-24	11-12
POM5	12-14	9-10	29.2-33	14-14	15.3-17.3	17-23	17-17	12-13
POM6	14-14	9-9		14-14	15.3-17.3	17-17		12-12
POM 7								
POM 8								
POM9	8-9	12-12		13-14	17.3-17.3	18-18	17-17	11-12
POM10		10-10		11-15	12-13			11-11
POM 11								
POM12	11-14	9-10	16-29.2	13-14	11-17.3	21-23		11-13

Table 16: results of bioinformatic analyses for the reconstruction of the mitochondrial genome.

Lab ID	# of Raw Reads	# of Merged Reads	# Mapped Reads after RMDup	Mean Coverage	average fragment length	Hg
Pom-1	2557158	1201083	240080	809,9197	55,9	T2b7a2
Pom-2	1242948	563603	129871	433,6295	55,32	H4a1a1a
Pom-3	1166232	518584	131635	446,4671	56,2	K1a2
Pom-4	1726438	751752	202959	632,0716	51,6	U7a
Pom-5	2056034	893788	229167	708,9081	51,25	I2
Pom-6	2800168	1231777	354743	1327,3615	62,0	I2
Pom-7	1524736	672345	162127	477,2076	48,77	H9a
Pom-8	255258	111175	15685	48,7931	51,54	K1a2
Pom-9	2832782	1281725	274150	1045,3301	63,18	U7a
Pom-10	363426	165410	8510	29,1754	56,8	H7d3
Pom-11	349310	157059	28629	96,7101	55,97	H13a1
Pom-12	3585520	1583978	243753	822,3547	55,9	I2

The authenticity of the consensus sequences obtained was evaluated by analyzing the degradation patterns at the ends of the DNA molecules and by identifying diagnostic positions that differ from a database of 311 modern human mtDNAs. As shown in Table 17, all evaluated parameters indicate that the results obtained are authentic.

Table 17: all evaluated parameters indicate that the results obtained are authentic.

Lab ID	mapDamage Result		ContamMix Result
	C to T (%)	G to A (%)	MAP Authentic (95% C.I.)
Pom-1	10,24	10,73	99,36
Pom-2	9,58	9,18	99,61
Pom-3	8,07	8,31	97,97
Pom-4	6,08	6,36	98,91
Pom-5	6,06	6,17	99,21
Pom-6	3,69	3,84	99,99
Pom-7	7,19	7,21	99,84
Pom-8	9,94	8,52	99,96
Pom-9	4,35	4,39	99,95
Pom-10	6,02	6,62	98,71
Pom-11	6,34	6,70	99,89
Pom-12	10,88	11,7	99,16

By combining anthropological information with the genetic data obtained through the NGS approach and STR analysis, it was possible to identify samples belonging to the same individual as well as the kin relationships within the group under investigation. The results can be summarized as follows:

Pom-4 and Pom-9, both males with the same mitochondrial profile and 19 shared loci (with presumed allelic dropouts): same individual;

Pom-5 and Pom-6, both females with the same mitochondrial profile and 15 shared loci (with presumed allelic dropouts): same individual;

Pom-12 and Pom-5/6 share the same mitochondrial profile and show a half-shared STR locus profile across 19 typed loci, assuming an allelic dropout in Pom-12 at locus D18S51. Additionally, they exhibit P0 values compatible with a first-degree relationship: Pom-12 is the mother of Pom-5/6;

Pom-3 and Pom-8 show the same mitochondrial profile; however, while the biological sex is known for Pom-3 (female), this information is missing for Pom-8. STR profiles could not be obtained for either sample. Therefore, based on their age class and mitochondrial data, we can hypothesize that Pom-3 is the mother of Pom-8.

After the initial exploratory sequencing, the six individuals with endogenous DNA levels above 20% were selected for a second sequencing round in order to reach an average coverage of 0.1x. Given the particular excavation context, these samples were treated differently from the 12 deep-shotgun individuals (analyzed previously), as the aim of the study was not

demographic inference but the identification of potential kin relationships between adults and subadults. For this reason, in addition to the first 12 analyzed samples, five further skeletal samples (Pom-8.1, Pom-8.2, Pom-10.1, Pom-10.2, and Pom-11.1) were processed to obtain a complete overview of the minimum number of individuals present in the room and their kin relationships.

Furthermore, samples with an endogenous DNA percentage higher than 20% underwent additional sequencing to reach an average coverage of $\sim 1\times$, while those with endogenous levels below 20% were subjected to nuclear DNA target enrichment, as described in the relevant section of "Materials and Methods." Since these latter data are still under analysis, only the results obtained for the six deep-shotgun sequenced samples are described below. Processing of the raw data using the pipeline described in the "Materials and Methods" section led to the reconstruction of the genomes, whose main statistics are reported in [Table 18](#).

Table 18: Main statistics for the 6 deep-shotgun-sequenced samples.

ID campione	Reads grezze	Reads mappanti	DNA endogeno (%)	Coverage medio	Coverage 1X (%)
Pom-1	100365528	7341543	27.768	0.1185	10.73
Pom-2	140110200	4839696	13.072	0.0763	7.17
Pom-3	62713832	6712805	46.02	0.1093	10.11
Pom-4/9	44097032	6284752	62.912	0.096	8.95
Pom-5/6	61356854	7849451	57.732	0.1191	10.91
Pom-12	77471484	6707855	35.452	0.1087	10.02

For the two male individuals, the absence of nuclear contamination was demonstrated ($-0.002057 \pm 2.09E-03$ and $-0.002494 \pm 2.54E-03$) using the method that estimates the degree of heterozygosity on the X chromosome. In addition, Y-chromosome haplogroups were identified using the software Yleaf2.0, modifying the parameter $-r 2$, which had initially produced no results due to the low sequencing coverage. By setting the flag to 1 ($-r 1$), the haplogroups shown in [Table 19](#) were determined.

Table 19: Y-chromosome haplogroups identified by lowering the minimum number of reads.

ID campioni	Aplogruppo chrY	Marcatoti validi
Pom-1	R1b1a1b	4114
Pom-4/9	E1b1b1b~	3598

Mapping to chrY markers to 1. The 6 shotgun $1\times$ genomes ([Table 18](#)) were genotyped for the HO and 1240K SNP arrays. [Table 22](#) reports the SNP coverage of the individuals for the two panels used.

Table 20: SNPs covered following genotyping performed on both the Human Origins panel (HO, 597,573 total SNPs) and the 1240K panel (1,233,013 total SNPs).

ID Samples	SNPs covered 1240K	SNPs covered HO
Pom-1	175159	95680
Pom-2	115731	62733
Pom-3	160598	86089
Pom-4/9	146049	78261
Pom-5/6	175670	94027
Pom-12	159543	85803

Kinship analysis on the shotgun genomes, performed using the software READ [MK10], which is designed for low-coverage ancient genomes, enabled the identification of a first-degree relationship between Pom-5/6 and Pom-12 (Figure 7). These individuals—a woman and a child—share the same mitochondrial haplogroup (Table 18), suggesting that they could be mother and daughter.

Figure 10: Kinship analysis performed as described in Section 3.4.7. The graph on the left shows the degree of relatedness between pairs of individuals, while the graph on the right displays the proportion of differing alleles (P0).

The PCA was built using present-day populations from Western Eurasia and North Africa, onto which the ancient comparative populations and all six individuals from the “Room of the Skeletons” were projected. As shown in Figure 8, it is interesting to observe how individuals recovered from the same location are distributed across all lines of variability of modern Eurasian populations. This indicates a remarkably high genetic diversity within a very small group of individuals from Pompeii. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that individuals linked by a

first-degree relationship—specifically the mother–daughter pair (Pom-12 and Pom-5/6)—are positioned far apart in the PCA, suggesting a paternal ancestry completely different from the maternal one. Pom-12 clusters with the variability of present-day western European populations and, when compared to ancient populations, appears distant from the variability of Imperial populations from the Italian peninsula, instead approaching contemporaneous French individuals and Roman-period individuals from the British provinces. Pom-5, by contrast, clusters with the variability of present-day central Italian populations, at a short distance from other Italian Imperial individuals. To complete the investigation of kinship within the room, the genomes of the missing samples (Pom-7, Pom-8, Pom-10, and Pom-11—each showing low endogenous DNA preservation) will be reconstructed using 1240K SNP-capture enrichment, as an endogenous DNA percentage above 0.15% is sufficient for this method. Additionally, a second sampling from newly available human remains is planned for some of these individuals.

Figure 8: a. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based on genomic variability from 61 present-day populations of Western Eurasia and North Africa genotyped on the HO panel, onto which the six individuals from the “Room of the Skeletons” and the comparative ancient samples were projected. b. Detail of the PCA highlighting the mother (Pom-12) and daughter (Pom-5) individuals.

2.3.3 Methodology

Archaeological Material. A total of 173 human remains from the Applied Research Laboratory of Pompeii were processed, originating from excavation campaigns conducted in different periods and in various areas of the ancient city. Only the remains of individuals who lost their

lives during the AD 79 eruption were included, and different sampling procedures were applied depending on the specific specimen. Information is provided in Table 1.

Case Study: The Room of the Skeletons. Among the numerous human remains recovered in Pompeii, a particularly noteworthy case is the individuals found in the so-called “Room of the Skeletons,” part of the Casa del Giardino in Regio V. Over the centuries, the site underwent repeated excavations—even prior to the Bourbon period—often including looting in search of valuables carried by those fleeing the eruption. Because early excavations (from 1748) did not aim to preserve the archaeological context, the room shows signs of tampering, such as scattered bones and wall perforations.

Despite this, around 11 individuals were identified, including one adult whose skull was crushed by a falling roof tile during a pyroclastic surge. Adults were found near the entrance (Pom-2, Pom-3, Pom-10, Pom-12), while subadults were found toward the back (Pom-1, Pom-4, Pom-5, Pom-6, Pom-7, Pom-8, Pom-9, Pom-11).

Laboratory Methods. Human remains were processed in the dedicated ancient DNA facility of the University of Florence with strict contamination-prevention protocols. Sampling included petrous bones, teeth, and some postcranial remains. Cleaning involved soil removal and UV irradiation. Petrous bones were sectioned with diamond blades, and approximately 50 mg of powder was taken from the dense region. Teeth were sampled through the root to preserve the crown. DNA extraction followed the [D13] protocol optimized for short fragments. Extracts were quantified with Qubit, and double-stranded Illumina libraries were built using half-UDG treatment to preserve terminal damage. Libraries were indexed, purified, quality-checked, and sequenced in a light shotgun run (5M reads/sample). For individuals from the Room of the Skeletons, targeted enrichment was carried out for mtDNA and ~1.24M nuclear SNPs using Twist probes. Extracts from these individuals were also quantified with Quantifiler Trio and genotyped with the GlobalFiler STR system.

Bioinformatic Analysis. Exploratory shotgun data were processed using EAGER, including adapter removal, merging, quality filtering, hg19 alignment with bwa aln, PCR duplicate removal, and mapDamage analysis. Individuals exceeding 20% endogenous DNA and showing characteristic aDNA damage were selected for deep shotgun sequencing. Deep shotgun reads were quality-checked, merged, aligned, filtered ($MQ \geq 30$), deduplicated, and damage-rescaled. These BAM files were used for downstream analyses. For target-enriched samples, reads were trimmed, merged, and mapped to rCRS using CircularMapper. Consensus sequences were generated with SAMtools, and authenticity was assessed by terminal damage and comparison with mtDNA databases. Contamination was estimated via likelihood-based approaches.

Sex determination followed the Ry metric, distinguishing males and females based on Y-chromosome read proportions. Nuclear contamination in males was estimated with ANGSD [KAN14] using X-chromosome heterozygosity; mitochondrial contamination was estimated

with schmutzi [R15]. Uniparental haplogroups were identified using schmutzi + Haplogrep2 (mtDNA) and Yleaf (Y-chr markers).

Genotyping and PCA. Pseudo-haploid calls were made using pileupCaller on the 1240K and Human Origins SNP panels. Data were merged with public datasets and used to compute PCA with smartpca. Ancient individuals were projected onto modern genetic variation.

Kinship Analysis. READ software was used to assess kinship up to the second degree among individuals in the Room of the Skeletons, using 1 Mb genome windows and P0 allele-difference metrics.

Whole-Genome and Genotype Likelihoods. For individuals with deep shotgun sequencing, whole-genome analyses were performed on neutral regions (excluding coding, repeats, CpG islands). ANGSD was used to compute genotype likelihoods, allele frequencies, and polymorphism significance across shared genomic regions.

Comparative Dataset. A reference dataset of ancient genomes from the Mesolithic to the Roman Imperial period was assembled, including WHG, CHG, Anatolian Neolithic, Iranian Neolithic, and Steppe ancestries. All reference genomes were reprocessed with the same pipeline.

PCAngsd and NgsAdmix. PCAngsd computed covariance matrices from genotype likelihoods for low-coverage genomes. NgsAdmix estimated individual ancestry proportions testing $K=2-10$, producing final admixture profiles.

2.3.4 Conclusions

To date, the research project has involved the sampling of more than 170 human remains from different areas of the Archaeological Park of Pompeii, all belonging to victims of the AD 79 eruption of the Somma-Vesuvius complex. The sampling of the remains was carried out with the aim of recovering and studying ancient DNA (aDNA) in order to clarify, in the case of the "Room of the Skeletons," the presence of kinship relationships hypothesized by anthropologists after the discovery of the human remains and, more generally, to investigate the genetic variability of the individuals who, at that historical moment, lived in or were present in the ancient city of Pompeii. The first results, obtained from the exploratory sequencing of such a large number of human remains belonging to the victims of the eruption, confirm the presence of highly conserved endogenous DNA preserved over the centuries. Through a multidisciplinary approach applied to the human remains from the "Room of the Skeletons," we were able to answer many of the questions that emerged during the discovery of the site. Only women and children managed to find temporary shelter inside the room of the domus during the final phases of the eruption. Despite the sequencing depth of the six individuals being below 1x, methods and tools specifically designed for the analysis of degraded, low-

coverage genomes were successfully applied, revealing that two of them share a first-degree kinship, although the presence of additional blood relationships among other individuals cannot be excluded and will be evaluated through more detailed analyses currently underway. Finally, a high degree of genetic variability was found within such a small group of individuals; even the “mother–daughter” pair is located in distant regions of the PCA, with the mother overlapping present-day French and English populations—close to individuals from the Roman provinces in Britain—and the daughter aligning with the genetic variability observed in central Italy during the Imperial period. At present, the genomic approaches used were of two types and yielded very similar results, but the one based on whole-genome data and on the calculation of genotype likelihoods (GL) provided stronger statistical support for the conclusions.

Since most ancient genomes in the NGS era are sequenced at medium–low depth (due to low endogenous DNA content or the limited financial feasibility of sequencing large sample sets), likelihood-based approaches represent a robust method for their analysis.

Using likelihoods made it possible to extend the analysis to a larger number of genomic positions—some of which are excluded from reference panels commonly used in molecular anthropology—allowing for finer characterization of the individuals under study and leading to more robust conclusions. Moreover, factors that would otherwise introduce uncertainties into genotype calling were taken into account (low nucleotide read quality, low regional coverage with the risk of sampling a single chromosome in diploid organisms, poor mapping quality, etc.).

In this work, for the first time in a concrete way, we demonstrate the feasibility of applying GL-based analytical methods to study genetic variability and ancestry in ancient populations of major historical interest, whose genomes are necessarily reconstructed at low coverage.

Population genomic analyses demonstrate, based on such an extensive sample, that intra-population genetic variability in ancient Pompeii was high compared to that already documented for the same period in the capital of the Empire (and its surrounding areas), despite Pompeii being a much smaller city that experienced economic and cultural growth following the relocation of Roman nobility. Individuals from Pompeii are not only different from each other—as shown by the broad dispersion in PCA and by Admixture analyses—but their genomic profiles also differ from those of other Imperial-period individuals from the Italian peninsula, who are genetically much more homogeneous. In fact, unlike other Imperial individuals who show limited genetic affinity to populations from the foreign provinces of the Empire (except in rare cases), several individuals from Pompeii appear to share genetic components with them, particularly with English and French populations. Furthermore, in some cases, Pompeii shows the persistence of the genomic profile characteristic of pre-Roman Italic populations.

This highlights the dynamic nature of Pompeii, an important Mediterranean port city, where the presence of individuals with diverse and uncommon origins—considering populations in nearby territories—may reflect ancient and long-standing, or more recent, contacts between

Roman populations and groups both within and outside the Empire for economic, occupational, and military reasons.

In this regard, future examination of isotopic data will be particularly informative, as isotopes provide insights into individuals' birthplace and childhood environment. This will make it possible to understand whether the diversity observed in Pompeii's population reflects migrations occurring within the last generation prior to the eruption (as isotopes can reveal) or earlier movements (which would have left detectable signatures in the genome).

ONGOING ANALYSES

Population genomic analyses are currently underway on 45 individuals (those with an endogenous DNA percentage $\geq 20\%$) for whom full genomes with 1x coverage have been obtained. All analyses (PCA, Admixture, Identity by Descent, and Runs of Homozygosity) are being repeated using three different genotyping approaches—pseudo-haploid calling, maximum likelihood, and imputation—to identify the most reliable methodology. In addition, we are estimating phenotypic traits and investigating variants associated with potential genetic diseases.

Alongside population-level studies, we are examining specific contexts (beyond the “Room of the Skeletons”) that required a molecular target-enrichment strategy for individuals with low endogenous DNA.

Specifically, these contexts include:

- (i) Casa del Primo Piano, where anthropological studies identified eight individuals (adults and subadults) who died inside the house, perhaps while seeking shelter from the eruption. We are focusing particularly on identifying familial relationships.
- (ii) Two individuals from the Thermopolium, who may be related; kinship analyses are ongoing, as well as for the two casts from Civita Giuliana, for whom ancestry is also being investigated.
- (iii) The cavalryman found on Maiuri's horse, for whom analyses aimed at reconstructing phenotype and geographic origin are underway, despite the DNA being poorly preserved.

3. Conclusions

UNIBO Cultural Heritage Department has shown that an integrated analytical framework combining high-resolution dental histology, trace-element microprofiling, and computational modelling significantly enhances the reconstruction of developmental and physiological trajectories in archaeological populations. The joint application of classical histomorphometry and LA-ICP-MS provides a refined understanding of enamel formation, enabling a deeper comprehension of early-life stress episodes with improved temporal resolution and interpretative reliability. At the same time, advances in semi-automated cementum analysis offer a substantial methodological improvement for age-at-death estimation, reducing subjectivity and increasing reproducibility relative to traditional approaches.

While highly promising, this multi-disciplinary strategy also reveals challenges related to sample preservation, microstructural variability, and the need for further optimization of analytical framework. Nevertheless, the combined use of multi-analytical approaches establishes a more objective and biologically grounded framework for interpreting dental tissue and reconstructing ancient human life histories.

Overall, the studies conducted by the **Department of Chemistry of Unibo** demonstrate the value of integrating innovative analytical approaches to enhance the investigation, preservation, and interpretation of archaeological biomaterials. From the rapid, non-invasive characterization of burned bones and the assessment of cellulose preservation in ancient wood, to the long-term evaluation of amino acid stability in fossil enamel and the development of biomimetic receptors for amelogenin detection, each contribution expands the methodological toolkit available to archaeologists. Together, these results show how advances in spectroscopy, hyperspectral imaging, chemometrics, and bioinspired sensing can significantly improve sample selection, strengthen conservation strategies, and deepen our understanding of ancient biological materials across a wide range of contexts.

The **UNIFI (BIO)** project has involved sampling over 170 human remains from various areas of Pompeii, all belonging to victims of the AD 79 eruption. The goal is to extract and analyze ancient DNA to understand possible family relationships—such as those suspected in the “Room of the Skeletons”—and to explore the genetic diversity of Pompeii’s population at the time of the eruption.

Initial sequencing results show that the DNA is surprisingly well preserved, allowing researchers to apply advanced techniques suited for low-coverage and highly degraded genomes. In the “Room of the Skeletons,” where only women and children sought refuge during the final phase of the eruption, the analyses revealed that two individuals are first-degree relatives, though further genetic ties among the group are still being studied. Interestingly, despite their close relationship, the supposed “mother–daughter” pair shows markedly different genetic profiles, suggesting diverse ancestries: the mother aligns

genetically with ancient and modern populations from France and England, while the daughter resembles central Italian individuals from the Imperial period.

The use of whole-genome approaches and genotype likelihood (GL) methods—particularly useful for low-coverage ancient DNA—allowed the researchers to analyze many more genomic sites and draw more reliable conclusions. These analyses confirm that Pompeii's population was genetically diverse, even more so than populations in Rome during the same period. Individuals from Pompeii show varied ancestries, including links to regions such as France and England, as well as traces of older Italic populations, reflecting the city's dynamic role as a Mediterranean port with broad cultural and economic connections.

Future isotopic studies will help clarify whether this diversity reflects recent migration (detectable through isotopes) or older movements reflected only in the genome.

Ongoing analyses include detailed genomic studies on 45 individuals with sufficiently high-quality DNA, using multiple genotyping strategies to ensure robust results. Researchers are also investigating physical traits and potential genetic diseases, as well as studying smaller groups from specific archaeological contexts. These include:

- individuals from the *Casa del Primo Piano* to determine family relationships;
- two people from the *Thermopolium* and two casts from *Civita Giuliana* to evaluate kinship and ancestry;
- and a cavalryman found with his horse, for whom phenotype and geographic origins are being reconstructed despite poor DNA preservation.

Overall, the research is revealing a complex and diverse genetic landscape in ancient Pompeii, offering new insights into its population, mobility patterns, and cultural interactions shortly before the city's destruction.

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